

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

Project Acronym:	VITALISE
Project Title:	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure
Project Number:	101007990
Topic:	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme INFRAIA-02-2020 Integrating Activities for Starting Communities
Type of Action:	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Start date of the Project:	April 2021
Duration of the Project:	36 months

D7.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA3

(Version 3.0, 15/04/2024)

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Deliverable:	D7.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA3	
Work Package:	WP7	
Due Date:	31 March 2024	
Submission Date:	15 April 2024	
Lead Beneficiary:	INTRAS	
Version:	3.0	
Status:	Submitted	
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Keywords:	Joint Research Activities, Transitional Care, Results	
Nature:	R – Report	
Dissemination level:	PU - Public	

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Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	19/01/2024	INTRAS, LAUREA, LICALAB, AUTH, GAIA	Preparation of table of contents
0.2	26/02/2024	INTRAS	ToC final version aligned with other JRAs
0.3	28/03/2024	AUTH, UPM, INTRAS, LICALAB	Contributions integrated
0.4	28/03/2024	INTRAS	Formatting changes
1.0	28/03/2024	INTRAS	Version ready for review combined with the first review and editorial changes. Note: Some information is still to be completed in the <i>Harmonized Analysis across living Labs</i> section.
2.0	11/04/2024	INTRAS	Completion of the missing information in the <i>Harmonized Analysis across living Labs</i> section. Ready for Review 2.
3.0	12/04/2024	INTRAS	Changes after 2 nd review, document ready for submission

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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
JRA	Joint Research Activity
AHA	Active and Healthy Ageing
LL	Living Lab
RI	Research Infrastructure
EQ-5D	EuroQol 5 Dimensions
WHOQOL-BREF	World Health Organization Quality of Life - BREF
TUG	Timed Up and Go test
MoCA	Montreal Cognitive Assessment
MMSE	Mini-Mental State Examination
GDS	Geriatric Depression Scale
GSE-6	General Self-Efficacy Scale (6 items)
UEQ	User Experience Questionnaire
SUS	Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory

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VAS Stress	Visual Analog Stress Scale
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Executive summary

Although Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be a “key” to the integration of research and innovation processes in real-life settings, they still fail to provide and function according to unified and harmonized processes that are easily accessible and exploitable by academic and industrial researchers. VITALISE brings together Living Labs across Europe (and 1 outside Europe in Canada) to create a Thematic ecosystem of Living Labs in the Health and Wellbeing domain, aiming at creating synergies and transnational collaboration opportunities through innovative Joint Research Activities.

During VITALISE project three Joint Research Activities (JRAs) were implemented among the consortium Living Lab partners. These JRAs included state-of-the-art use cases that investigated AHA and chronic conditions in three important domains for the Health and Wellbeing Research. They were selected based on the consortium’s existing research studies and expertise: Rehabilitation, Transitional care and Everyday living environments (respectively JRA1, JRA2, JRA3).

The JRA of WP7 focused on the use of supportive technology for everyday living and data collection in everyday living context. We primarily aimed to gain insight in each living lab’s infrastructure and procedures to harmonise health and wellbeing living lab procedures and infrastructures in Europe and beyond, in the context of everyday living. Secondly, we aimed to investigate the use and applicability of innovative technologies in the context of various everyday living and Living Lab environments. Four of the five small-scale pilots were preceded by co-creation sessions, and one proceeded. This document presents an overview of the case studies performed in different countries.

1. Introduction

1.1. Description of the JRA process

The Joint Research Activities (JRAs) served as a test bed for all the internal harmonisation procedures, for assessing and improving the provided services, as well as the research cases that could be the basis for the external researchers through the transnational and virtual access procedures. Activities focused on three different domains in Living Lab Health & Wellbeing research: rehabilitation (WP5), transitional care (WP6) and everyday living environments (WP7).

To harmonize procedures as much as possible, **common JRA stand-up meetings** across WP5-6-7 were organised replacing the bi-weekly WP7 meetings from 31/5/22 onwards. During these meetings we exchanged ideas, challenges and improvements for the activities that we performed in the JRAs and the procedures we agreed upon (such as a standard template for scenario, report and data collection methods, as well as recruitment strategy, etc.). After the first intensive phase, these meetings were organised monthly instead of bi-weekly. A Teams folder called **JRAs general channel** was created to share materials and reports.

The primary aim of the initial co-creation sessions in phase 1 was to gather insights based on the daily living experiences of individuals with chronic illnesses, with a particular emphasis on the elderly suffering from both physical and cognitive impairments. This groundwork led to phase 2's small-scale pilot studies, which concentrated on several primary outcome measures: Quality of Life (QoL) assessments using tools like WHOQOL-BREF and EQ-5D, physical activity, and mobility measures such as the Timed Up and Go (TUG) test and chair stand test, cognitive status via Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) and Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE), social and emotional well-being assessed through the Lubben Social Network Scale, frailty risk and general self-efficacy measured by the Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS) and the General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE-6), and user experience evaluated with the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) and the System Usability Scale (SUS, Brooke, 1996). Additionally, study-specific data were collected, including the Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory (MFI) and the Visual Analog Stress Scale (VAS Stress), to provide a comprehensive overview of the participants' health and well-being, informing future interventions.

The primary goal shared across all JRA3 case studies was to collaboratively pinpoint the optimal methods, tools, and instruments for gathering both qualitative and quantitative big data within research settings that simulate everyday living environments. As the initiative progressed, this goal expanded to encompass JRA1 and JRA2 projects as well. The first step involved identifying the existing devices capable of collecting qualitative and quantitative data through digital biomarkers across the living labs of all three JRAs. Subsequently, small-scale case studies specific to each JRA were carried out to assess the effectiveness of these selected tools in capturing digital biomarkers across a variety of settings, including rehabilitation, transitional care, and daily living environments. While pursuing this shared objective, each case study also pursued its unique research goals, detailed further in the case study section. Concurrently, a modified online Delphi study was conducted to develop a taxonomy for categorizing and organizing the digital data collection and intervention tools used in the case studies. Following the completion of the case studies, the devices employed were organized according to this taxonomy, and examples of measurements and intervals were compiled to explore opportunities for creating hybrid personas driven by big data. The process culminated in discussions on the challenges and advantages of utilizing these devices for digital biomarker data collection, engaging insights from the case studies.

To keep track of progression of the JRAs, LiCalab created a **status report** Excel file called **Vitalise overview JRA activities** in which each partner regularly reported the status of his case study

(preparation, deployment phase, running phase). The preparation phase showed the participants' sample size and profile as well as the status of ethical approval. In the deployment phase we determined how many participants were contacted, screened and recruited, what the status of the information sessions was and, if applicable, whether technology was deployed. The running phase provided an overview of the data collection from pre, intermediary, and post measurements as well as data collection from devices, applications and software. Finally, the number of participants that completed the study was mentioned. Another tab in the file was meant to report discussions on challenges, actions required to resolve those, and lessons learned.

When the JRAs were finished, VILABS assessed the **socio-economic impact** of the JRA outcomes, gathering information from all Living Labs involved. This information is included at the end of the report.

1.2. Description of JRA3 - Everyday living environments

JRA3 (WP7) studied the use and applicability of innovative technologies in the context of various everyday living and Living Lab environments. Also studied the harmonized process and collection for developing big data–driven hybrid persona, which are hypothetical user archetypes created to represent a user community. An overview of the studies and the stakeholders involved in each study is presented in Table 2.

In phase 1, multiple international living labs organized **co-creation sessions**, involving potential end-users to gather insights on daily living environments and the application of innovative technologies, all grounded in Design Thinking principles. These sessions allowed participants to pinpoint specific challenges that led to low adherence in technology-assisted daily living programs and suggest improvements to current intervention tools. The focus was also on assessing the usability and acceptance of these technologies among key stakeholders, including doctors, patients, and the general public. The primary goal was to uncover any potential issues, such as feasibility or deployment challenges, especially in real-life contexts like the homes of older adults.

Furthermore, separate **small-scale pilots** were organised to test five innovative interventions or data collection technologies in practice using preliminary harmonised procedures (phase 2). A mixed-methods study design was adopted in which five (technological) interventions were implemented in everyday living environments across seven countries (Finland, Greece, Spain, Belgium, Hungary, Austria and Canada) to assess user experience and explore the (preliminary) effects of the implemented intervention. The research protocol comprised a variety of study designs, including pre-post designs, controlled studies, or a collaborative participatory research design. Following that testing period, usability of each intervention was evaluated in relation to Everyday Living supported by technology practices. Each Living Lab engaged end-users that experienced an intervention in everyday living environment or for everyday living support.

In Table 1, an overview is provided of all the engaged Living Labs of JRA3. Data collection of the co-creation sessions (phase 1) started in August 2022 and ended June 2023. Data collection of the small-scale pilot studies (phase 2) started in February 2023 and finished in March 2024.

Table 1. Overview of the Living Labs and organisations involved in JRA3

Abbreviation	Full (legal) name	Country
LAUREA	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	Finland
AUTH	Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis	Greece

GAIA	Association of Electronic and Information Technologies in the Basque Country	Spain
LiCalab	Living & Care Lab - Thomas More Kempen vzw	Belgium
TREBAG	TREBAG Intellectual Property and Project Manager Ltd	Hungary
INTRAS	Fundación INTRAS	Spain
AIT	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH	Austria
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	Greece
McGill	McGill University	Canada
CRIR	Centre for Interdisciplinary Research in Rehabilitation of Greater Montreal	Canada
UDEM	Université de Montréal	Canada

1.3. Purpose of the document

This document describes the results of all JRA3 activities: the co-creation sessions of phase 1 as well as the small-scale studies of phase 2 that were performed across the seven countries (Finland, Greece, Spain, Belgium, Hungary, Austria and Canada). Full protocols of the different case studies were presented in D7.1, and ethical approval preparations were displayed in D7.2.

1.4. Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1 Introduction** (this section) provides the description of the JRA process and JRA3 – Everyday Living supported by technology, the purpose of the document as well as its structure.
- **Section 2 Case Studies Overview** consists of the JRA3 case studies across the seven countries. First, the study is described, followed by the challenges encountered during execution. Next, outcomes and analyses are described. Finally, most important conclusions are shared.
- **Section 3 Harmonized Analysis across Living Labs.** This section comprises Living Lab harmonised services, JRA3 comparative results and challenges and the socio-economic impact assessment. It includes the description of the process for Cocreating a Harmonized Living Lab for Big Data–Driven Hybrid Persona Development.
- **Section 4 Recommendations for Everyday Living.** This section summarises the recommendations taken from all case studies.
- **Section 5. Conclusion** provides some concluding remarks for this deliverable.

2. Case Studies Overview

Table 2. Overview of co-creation sessions and small-scale pilot studies

AIT / LICALAB <i>Digital Coaching App</i>		CERTH <i>Net Zero Energy Buildings</i>	INTRAS <i>UX With Gradior Active</i>	LAUREA / GAIA / TREBAG <i>Multidimensional Physical Fitness</i>	McGill-CRIR / AUTH <i>Effects of a Museum Visit on Mobility, Cognition, and Well-being in People with Stroke</i>
Co-creation					
CP/Exp	NA	NA	6 therapists	LAUREA: co-creation 3 care professionals and interview 1 exercise expert (municipality) TREBAG: co-creation with 15 social care workers	AUTH: N/A McGill-CRIR: 8 museum personnel, 15 museum VIP members and 15 citizen who were visiting the museum
Pts/C	AIT: Intake interviews: N = 21 LICALAB: Co-creation: N = 5	NA	9 users	GAIA: 2 sessions, N=22 LAUREA: Co-creation 8 users TREBAG: NA	AUTH: session 1: N=4, session 2: N=8 McGill-CRIR: NA
Small-scale pilot studies					
Aim	AIT: N = 20 LICALAB: N = 20 Retirement +/- 3 years	N=18 (ranging from 55 years old to 70 healthy adults),	5 therapists and 45 users	LAUREA: Testing track N=200-400, Fitness tracker N=40, Senior service centre N=50 TREBAG: N=23 (55-85) older people; Pre-test, NW intervention, post-test GAIA: Pilot 1, N=30, age 65+; Pilot 2, N=9, age 75+	AUTH: N=20 (10 post stroke patients – 4 of which with mild aphasia & 10 healthy controls aged between 55-85 y.) McGill-CRIR: N=40 (10 post stroke patients without aphasia, 10 post stroke patients with aphasia, 20 healthy aging controls)
Status	AIT: N = 21 LICALAB: N = 19	N=18 (ranging from 55 years old to 70 healthy adults)	5 therapists and 20 users	LAUREA: Testing track N=383, Fitness tracker N=25, Senior	AUTH: 10 healthy controls & 1 post stroke patient with mild aphasia

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	Retirement +/- 3 years			service centre N=38 TREBAG: N=23 Av.age 72; Older women; Fitness tracker: 23	McGill-CRIR: N=25 (10 post stroke patients without aphasia, 5 post stroke patients with aphasia, 10 healthy adults)
IV	8-weeks application + diary	1-day multicomponent intervention for each participant (cognitive and physical tasks executed in a fully operational Smart Home Living Lab infrastructure.)	8-weeks application	LAUREA: Testing track: One time, Fitness tracker: 24 hours, Senior service centre: One time TREBAG: 1 day pre-test; 9 weeks intervention; 1 day post-testing	AUTH: One museum visit McGill-CRIR: Two museum visits

Note. CP = Care professionals with area of expertise, Exp = (Technical) experts, Pts = Patients, C = Citizens, MCI = Mind cognitive impairment, IV = Intervention details. NA = Not applicable.

2.1. Case Study 1. Digital Coaching App Impact on Self-efficacy and Well-being (AIT/Austria; LiCalab/Belgium)

Study description

Objective and Phases:

Supporting older adults' health and well-being in the transition from work to retirement requires a holistic perspective and needs to address physical, mental, and social aspects of life. In the following, we describe a pilot study aiming to investigate to what extent the ProSelf app can influence individuals' self-efficacy and well-being by motivating older adults to practice a healthy lifestyle. Moreover, the study analysed usability, learnability, and acceptance of the app. Assessing the potential effects of the ProSelf digital coaching app on well-being as well as insights regarding the app usage may throw light on the potential of digital coaching for helping retirees to maintain (and improve) social relationships and activities that could be put at risk by the withdrawal from their workplace.

The **coaching approach** of the app deployed for the study started with a query of the user's **current level of well-being** addressing three different areas: **physical, social, and mental well-being**. Based on the results of the query and personal goals, **individualized app-based interventions** in a variety of different domains (physical, mental, social) were provided aiming to motivate the target group to become and/or stay active. For the time of the trial, 55 different activities were offered by the prototype. The distribution of activities within the different areas could be adjusted by the participants. A community aspect was added to the application. It allowed people to connect based on geographical closeness or mutual interests, and to exchange personal messages or to set up and post events that other users can join (e.g., a joint walk or visiting the cinema).

The following **research questions** were defined for the case study:

1. What challenges do individuals face around retirement age and how do they experience this new phase of life?

2. To what extent does the ProSelf app influence individuals' self-efficacy and well-being?
3. How does the user assess the usability of the app?
4. What are potential design implications to further improve the app?

The pilot study was conducted in Austria (AIT) and Belgium (LiCalab) and comprised 3 phases: pre-test, field test and post-test. A **mixed methods approach** covered on the one hand qualitative data of the co-creation sessions and interviews. On the other hand, quantitative data were assessed using the following standardized questionnaires: The participants' **well-being** was evaluated using the **SF-36v2** (personal well-being), the **Lubben Scale** (social life) and the **GSE-6**, (adaptation to stress and chronic illness). In addition, user **experience and usability** of the application were assessed using the User Experience Questionnaire (**UEQ**) and the System Usability Scale (**SUS**). Data was collected between October 2022 and February 2023. All participants provided informed consent.

During the pre-test phase, which focused on the first research question, participants in both countries completed the set of five standardised questionnaires (SF-36v2, Lubben Scale, GSE-6, UEQ, SUS). In addition, a co-creation session in Flanders and interviews in Austria were conducted, both posing similar questions. The **co-creation session** in Belgium involved five participants who were (almost) retired. Participants discussed challenges and chances related to the phase of retirement, and we gained insight into participants' priorities in their daily life. Finally, we evaluated their acceptance of using an app to guide them towards a healthy lifestyle, concluded by more specific questions about the ProSelf app. Some of the co-creation participants were willing to take part in the field test. Others were recruited from the LiCalab panel. In Austria, **interviews** with all 21 field study participants allowed insights into the challenges and experiences concerning this new phase of life. Subsequently, participants who were interested to participate in the field trial received their dummy profile for using the digital coach and filled out the standardized questionnaires.

The ProSelf prototype was then tested in a **field trial** over a period of eight-weeks in order to answer the following research question: How can a digital coach support older adults in the transition from work to retirement to establish and maintain a healthy lifestyle? The provided activities (in the areas physical, mental, social well-being and retirement) were tailored to personal objectives that could be set within the app. The target group consisted of older adults in the transition from work to retirement, to whom a healthy lifestyle is important and who would like to change some habits in their lives. Healthy individuals aged 55 years or older, either recently retired or in the final three years before retirement, were invited to participate in the study through e-mail, newsletters, and social media posts. Overall, 40 participants from Austria and Belgium took part in the 8-week trial, of which 8 dropped out throughout the testing. Halfway the field test, all standardised questionnaires except for the Lubben Scale were completed.

During the post-test phase, the usability of the application was assessed and potential design implications to further improve the app were identified. Once again, the set of five standardised questionnaires was completed. In Austria, interviews took place with the participants, whereas in Belgium a co-creation workshop was organised.

Execution and Challenges

The curiosity and motivation of participants decreased over the course of the study, mainly due to the limited number of activities that are currently available in both languages.

The use of the MIRO board enabled the two organisations to effectively and efficiently work together in order to identify themes and sub-themes in the qualitative data, even if they were not working on it simultaneously.

For the conference paper we prepared, we decided to focus on qualitative data because of the limited word count. This is why we also concentrate on this qualitative part when describing the analysis and results in this deliverable. However, we are currently working on the analyses of the quantitative part as well, although results are not yet available.

Outcomes and Analysis

Data analysis

The online questionnaires were **quantitatively analysed** using descriptive statistical analyses (SPSS). **Multiple t-tests** will be performed to investigate whether differences arise between the different times of testing for personal well-being, social life, and adaptation to stress and chronic illness. For the **qualitative data analysis**, all interviews, notes from the telephone interviews and content of the co-creation sessions were **transcribed** and a **thematic analysis** was applied to the transcripts and notes. Since two organizations from two different European countries were involved in the implementation of the study and the data analysis, a shared **Miro Board** was set up to ensure that both organizations could collaboratively work on the data analysis. A collaborative and iterative heuristic analysis process was followed. First, **key themes were identified and discussed** between the organizations. Afterwards the transcripts and notes were reviewed again by both organizations. The categories were then reorganized and refined during joint online meetings and sub-themes were identified. In the following, we focus on presenting the qualitative findings and discussing the main results.

Outcomes

The **qualitative data analysis** revealed **four key themes**, that already reflect the potential of the mobile coaching app and its main pitfall:

- Reflection
 - The app provides tips to increase participants' awareness for different aspects in life: practicing thankfulness, being more optimistic, reflecting memories etc.
 - A lot of the participants appreciated and valued those mental activities.
- Action
 - Different aspects of the app supported the users to become more active - physically but also socially.
 - The suggested daily activities were considered appealing, stimulating, engaging, and motivating and participants gave very positive feedback to them.
 - However, the curiosity and motivation of participants decreased over the course of the study, mainly due to the limited number of activities that are currently available in both languages and also because the suggested activities were sometimes inappropriate (too easy) for already active participants.
 - The interviews revealed that some users do not like to connect with others due to a variety of different reasons, e.g., they prefer face-to-face contacts or did not like to connect with strangers.
- Confirmation
 - We found that the app also confirmed users that they already have a good and healthy lifestyle, which motivated some participants when getting aware of that.
- Transition

- Participants raised the need to further personalize the physical activities to specific needs (such as health-, age- or accident-related restrictions) and to provide more different, but also more advanced activities for those who are already quite active.

The **quantitative data analysis** is still ongoing.

Conclusions

Recommendations and Lessons Learned

The study showed that the holistic approach of the digital coach had potential to encourage older adults to become and/or stay active, thus, support health and well-being of the target group on various levels. In particular, the mental activities were appreciated by all participants who took part in the trial and supported them beyond exercise and physical activities. The findings show that confirmation could play a significant role to motivate users, who are not so active now but have the goal of becoming active. Hence, activities which can be easily accomplished or that participants are already doing might be as important as challenging ones.

The lessons that we learned are on the one hand, that personalization (e.g., adapting the level of difficulty of activities) plays a vital role and should be further developed and refined in the future. On the other hand, we saw that the number of activities (55) was quite small for a period of eight weeks of use.

Another issue concerned the recruitment of participants. We've noticed that our sample consisted of highly motivated older individuals often aware of the importance of a healthy lifestyle on their health and already doing a good job with regard to daily activities in the targeted health areas. It might be more challenging to attract older adults that are less active at the moment, although they would perhaps benefit the most from using a digital coach.

The results of this study will be presented at the dHealth conference in Vienna, Austria, 7-8 May 2024 (<https://dhealth.at/>).

2.2. Case Study 2. Net Zero Energy Buildings Smart Home Living Lab (CERTH/Greece)

Study description

Objective and Phases: Briefly state the study's aim and outline the main phases (preparation, deployment, running, assessment), including any ethical and legal considerations (e.g. if any relevant variation regarding the protocol).

The primary aim of nZEB Smart Home was to test and train cognitive and physical tasks in a fully operational Smart Home Living Lab infrastructure in order to indicate the additive effects and interrelation of physical exercise and cognitive training towards cognition maintenance and physical performance in older adults.

To prove the added value of combined physical and cognitive interventions enabled by eHealth technologies, web applications and wearable sensors, a multi-component intervention has been designed and administered in a pilot feasibility study. A holistic approach of physiological monitoring during exercise, in lab-based interventions, balance distribution assessment, EEG measurements during Meditation task and activities of daily living execution in virtual environments has been applied

in the rapid prototyping and novel technologies' demonstration infrastructure of nZEB smart home of Information Technologies Institute (ITI). Case Study 2 entitled "Use of nZEB Smart Home services as a controlled lab environment to guide real life case studies of older adults" placed emphasis on the exploitation of combined physical and cognitive interventions enabled by eHealth technologies, virtual environments' potential, web applications and wearable sensors for the improvement of physical and cognitive status of older adults.

Figure 1. nZEB Smart Home services as a controlled lab environment

Technological resources used

In the present study a specific target group of healthy older adults had the opportunity to test and experience a range of technologies (sensors, for physiological monitoring, cognitive virtual games, eHealth apps and video assisted exercises of yoga sessions). In particular health-related IoT and sensor technologies such as Empatica E4 (<https://www.empatica.com/research/e4/>) wearable sensors and Muse EEG as well as web applications were incorporated in order to measure physical and brain activity and enable the extraction of valuable data such as patterns and biometric attributes. Sensors for physiological monitoring, cognitive virtual games (e.g. virtual reality brain training games for MCI detection), and a virtual coach for physical activity promotion. More specifically, mental and physical exercises, such as cognitive games and physical fitness programs in the form of "yoga" along with stretching exercises and Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) relaxation and mindfulness techniques, were implemented according to user fitness level and preferences.

Development

To achieve the goals of nZEB Smart Home pilot three activities were conducted: a. design of the overall theoretical framework of CERTH/ITI study based on concrete innovation process phases and services as Home-based simulated Lab environment- perform specific activities (e.g. virtual coach, yoga, apps), Assessment of several ADLs and other parameters (e.g., financial capacity etc.), Assessment of the usability/acceptance of the technology (e.g., sensors, Apps, Exercises/Brain Games, wearables) & Co-design in smart home interventions, b. careful design of study protocol and pilot sessions c. co-creation activities with healthcare professionals to assess psychological and physiological parameters such as balance and stability, flexibility and joint, health, regulation of blood pressure, mindfulness, stress and intensity.

D7.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA3

Figure 2. Some sensors, Apps, Exercises/Brain Games, wearables assessed

Data collection phase 1: Small scale pilot

The small-scale pilot study was implemented at the rapid prototyping and novel technologies' demonstration infrastructure of nZEB smart home of Information Technologies Institute (ITI) located in Thessaloniki, Greece. In the fully operational and demonstration infrastructure of nZEB smart home participants experienced cognitive and physical training to reach better cognitive and physical health. Also, among the main goals of the experimental study was to evaluate nZEB Smart Home services and technologies assessing their usability and acceptance by healthy aging target groups. The pilot operation involved 18 healthy older adults and one physiotherapist. The selection process was based on a pre-screening via telephone for age, inactivity, and "willingness to participate" criteria, and if eligible, scheduled for formal screening. Concrete criteria have been defined and followed with consistency. The study is planned to run over four phases: Phase 1, Recruitment pre-planning, Phase 2, Participant's recruitment, Phase 3: Session design, Phase 4: Outcome assessment. Also, usability and acceptance assessment has been performed through validated questionnaires and digital biomarkers for cognitive state and neuropsychological evaluation. The intervention period for participants spanned one month, through ten action steps were required for the participant to complete the protocol, in a specific course of action (Table 1). The full duration per participant was 65-70 minutes.

Table 3. Protocol Sessions

	Session	Duration		Session	Duration
1	Empatica & Insole Set-up	5 min	6	Muse Session Resting	1 min
2	Insole measurement	1 min	7	Muse Session Meditation	10 min
3	Yoga Session	15 min	8	Muse Session Resting	1 min
4	Insole measurement	1 min	9	Banking App	5 min
5	Muse Set-up	10 min	10	Virtual Supermarket	15 min

Within sessions, psychological and physiological parameters were assessed such as balance and stability, flexibility and joint, health, regulation of blood pressure, mindfulness, stress and intensity.

Figure 3. Snapshots from the sessions with participants

Data collection phase 2: Co-creation sessions

Before the execution of the initial pilot phase, co-creation sessions were organized to delve into professionals' perspectives and approach of the proposed technologies and to receive their feedback on the characteristics of technologies usage, acceptance and suggested points to improve the services planned to be provided.

The co-creation sessions took place in online discussion on 28 February 2023. Six experienced psychologists attend this meeting and pilot researchers demonstrated the digital tools that will be used. After the teleconference two activities followed: a. a questionnaire about users' requirements has been provided to be filled in by the healthcare professionals b. conceptualize professionals' response.

Activity 1: Identifying Requirements and Needs

- For what exact purpose do you use similar tools (e.g research, clinical purposes, for monitoring and support of the elderly in their daily life and/or emotional and mental strengthening exercises, creation of biomarkers for patient's clinical picture, useful in the future)?
- Could the technologies recommended be useful to your daily professional routine?
- In your opinion, what conditions (e.g. legal, social, ethical, etc.) should the proposed technologies/applications meet in order to be fully acceptable for use?
- Are there any legal, social, ethical issues that would prevent you from using the demonstrated technologies?
- What factors do you think could affect your acceptance of apps?

Activity 2: Envisioning the Ideal Technology and Program

Internal meetings and discussions among the multidisciplinary team of CERTH have been held about the holistic approach of social care of older adults to conceptualise the use of combined interventions and sophisticated intervention methods, such as yoga exercises properly fitted to older adults' needs and preferences. For the yoga video exercises, participants were instructed to follow the instructions, but they had the option to skip any exercise that felt uncomfortable in order to receive solely positive effects for older adults' health and cognition, joining physical postures with breathing exercises and meditation. Also, balance training, flexibility, strength, increased muscle tone and improved mood.

Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) and breathing practices cultivate positive thoughts, relax the mind, and enhance the mind-body connection.

Execution and Challenges

Progress and Barriers:

The springboard of the present feasibility study was the Greek medicine and philosophy notion of body and spirit balance. Targeting to address this necessity, multimodal assessment and training of motor function, physiology and cognition were conducted to explore the effects of joined activities that can improve mental health and provide better health and well-being.

The execution of the feasibility study showed the promising role of smart homes and LL environments to observe human behaviour while monitoring and controlling the indoor environment and diverse groups of participants joined physical and cognitive activities.

Challenges and opportunities to be addressed in future work include additional data collection for different groups of participants, will make possible the differentiation between groups (e.g. healthy and mild cognitive impairment) based on similar metrics to those discussed in the present work. Work towards further analysis of the collected data may lead to more efficient assessment and richer insights.

Ethics and legislation

LLs are paradigms of research solutions and spaces of open innovation that enable inclusive design. However, during the participatory design of LLs solutions and the initiation and implementation of novel technological approaches potential ethical issues and problems emerged from data information retrieval in LLs environments. To this end, a concrete methodology and procedure is considered of high importance in terms of CERTH/ITI living lab to be followed in order to achieve ethical awareness. Special attention has been paid on ethics, privacy, and security issues related to participants' rights and data management. More specifically, the specificity of the living lab environment has been considered to establish recruitment procedures and pilot' operation in alignment with an ethical approach and in compliance with legal requirements.

From the early recruitment process and experimentation phase of living lab, a process fully compliant with GDPR requirements was designed and implemented for candidate explicit awareness about research original purposes, methods and experiments' details.

In alignment with ethical and legal requirements, the study received an ethical approval of CERTH research centre ethical committee. The overall consent procedure was in consistency with EU ethical and legal requirements. A written consent was an ethics related prerequisite for the participation in the study.

Outcomes

For cognitive and physical outcomes in the LL context a set of devices and apps were used to evaluate older adults' physiological status jointly with participants' cognitive function in terms of daily activities execution. The evaluation methodology was based on key performance indicators (KPIs) and included scenarios/sessions in the following activities:

1. Physiological Monitoring during exercise
2. Balance distribution assessment
3. EEG measurements during Meditation Task

4. Activities of daily living execution

Within sessions, psychological and physiological parameters were assessed such as balance and stability, flexibility and joint, health, regulation of blood pressure, mindfulness, stress and intensity.

Analysis

The cognitive performance and physical function of 18 healthy adults, aged 55 to 70 years, were assessed to evaluate the significant impact of a holistic approach in lab-based interventions, establishing a correlation between cognitive and physical health. The study design methods included a) physiological monitoring during exercise, b) balance distribution assessment, c) EEG measurements during Meditation task and d) activities of daily living execution using a Banking transaction and a Virtual Supermarket web application.

Figure 4. Virtual scenarios (a. Banking transaction; b. virtual supermarket)

For cognitive and physical outcomes in the LL context a set of devices and apps were used to evaluate older adults' physiological status jointly with participants' cognitive function in terms of daily activities execution. Study results stressed the strong interconnection between physical and cognitive activities and the validity of the multicomponent intervention in real settings. According to study results and more specifically the physiological monitoring, a secure cloud platform offered by E4 Empatica was an effective environment for valuable insights regarding the participant's physiological response to the exercise task. In insoles balance distribution assessment, beneficial insights have been gained that may serve as early indicators of potential impact of the platform. Given that mindfulness meditation is associated with various benefit, EEG measurements during the specific task was able to assess participant's cognitive response to the task and observe differences between resting and meditation sessions.

Conclusions

Recommendations and Lessons Learned:

The feasibility study was successful in incorporating and combining various hardware and software solutions in exercise and meditation tasks as well as in simulations of everyday activities of the participants. Daily living activities in virtual environments through the Banking app and the Virtual Supermarket applications attracted participants' strong interest. Both tasks were successful in simulating daily activities of the participants, respectively a bank transaction and a daily visit to the supermarket for shopping performance.

Additional data collection is needed for extracting more features and valuable insights. Piloting with different groups and more participants will enable differentiating between groups using the extracted features and similar metrics. The execution of the feasibility study showed the promising role of smart

homes and LL environments to observe human behaviour while monitoring and controlling the indoor environment and diverse groups of individuals joined physical and cognitive activities.

2.3. Case Study 3. UX With Grador Active for Physical Training Reinforcing Dual Task Performance (INTRAS LL – MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living /Spain)

Study description

Objective:

The primary goal of this case study was to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the Grador Active prototype, focusing on usability, learnability, acceptability, and overall user experience, particularly emphasizing its ease of use, enjoyment, and perceived value within active and healthy aging programs. This evaluation included a pilot test of an outdated digital physical training system, complemented by a co-creation cycle involving older adults and therapists. These activities provided critical insights that informed an investment strategy for developing a service that employs AI for accurate posture detection and VR for immersive therapy, aiming to markedly enhance user engagement and outcomes. The findings from this case study were instrumental in understanding key user experience factors and in crafting hybrid personas using big data, in line with the initially described harmonized research protocol.

Technological resources used:

In this study, participants were provided with Grador Active. This is a physical and cognitive training system that combines motor and cognitive activities for independent and unrelated purposes (Dual Task). It incorporates controlled physical exercises (aerobic, strength, balance and flexibility exercises) using motion capture technologies (Microsoft Kinect). The programme consists of a Kinect v2 (Microsoft), a computer and a good-sized screen or projector, and a server component that provides the content and collects the data. Two units were installed and configured at the INTRAS Foundation clinic.

Minimum requirements: HP All-in-One 24-DF0043NS Intel Core i5-1035G1/8GB/512GB SSD/23.8" Touch; Grador APP software for windows (available through the Grador management website: <https://gestion.gradior.es>); Kinect Version 2.

The study has established the pillars in the decision-making process for the investment in the upgrade of this prototype.

Development

To achieve this goal, two distinct activities were conducted. The UX data collection during an 8-week program implementing the then-current Grador Active prototype was of major relevance for the second action carried out after the pilot. This second action focused on conducting a co-creation sprint to understand the challenges to optimize the program and its implementation in real environments and services (e.g., exploring ideal workflows).

Data collection phase 1: Small scale pilot

The small-scale pilot study was conducted at the INTRAS Headquarters, located at C/Martin Santos Romero N° 1 (47016, Valladolid), involving five therapists and twenty end-users. Participants were recruited by the INTRAS Neuropsychology Clinic's professionals, based on established inclusion criteria and confirmed through clinical and neuropsychological assessments.

D7.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA3

Inclusion criteria targeted volunteers aged 65+ who could consent and expressed concerns about potential mobility limitations due to physical decline, such as bone and muscle mass reduction, but who did not require heavy dependency support.

Exclusion criteria eliminated candidates with severe sensory challenges that affect device use, those unable to consent, individuals with psychiatric or neurological issues preventing study participation, cases of substance misuse, and those on antipsychotic drugs.

The study design was quasi-experimental, comprising pre-test, mid-term assessment, and post-test phases. Data collection for pre-test, mid-term assessment, and post-test measurements was conducted using validated clinical scales and custom questionnaires. Scores obtained before, during, and after the implementation of the treatment were documented, utilizing questionnaires such as the MMSE (Mini-Mental State Examination), MOCA, Geriatric Depression Scale GDS, UCLA Loneliness Scale, LUBBEN Social Life Scale, General Self-Efficacy Scale GSE, Quality of Life EQ-5D-3L, User Experience Questionnaire UEQ, System Usability Scale SUS, Tome Get Up and Go Test (TUG), and Assessment of the Level and Intensity of Physical Activity (RAPA). Additionally, information was gathered through Gradior Active, based on records of errors and successes in the program. Qualitative information was obtained through open questions at the conclusion of the pilot period.

The intervention period for participants spanned two months, featuring 30-minute sessions that combined physical and cognitive stimulation (dual task) using the Gradior Active program. Each session encompassed a variety of exercises designed to warm up the body, build strength, improve flexibility, boost aerobic capacity, and enhance memory and calculation skills. The program offered a diverse range of subcategories and levels of difficulty to cater to the individual needs and progress of participants.

Figure 5. Snapshots from the Sessions with Gradior Active VR system

Data collection phase 2: Co-creation sessions

Post-pilot, co-creation sessions were conducted in November 2023 at the INTRAS Headquarters in Valladolid to explore participants' views on the benefits of technologies and to solicit feedback for an ideal service design. Fifteen individuals, including end users and professionals, participated in sessions facilitated by INTRAS experts.

The sessions were tailored to the profiles of the participants. For those aged 60+, with self-expressed physical and cognitive health concerns, the two-hour sessions consisted of two main parts. The first part addressed their primary concerns related to aging and current health issues. The second part

involved devising technology-driven solutions fitting their needs and outlining the features of an ideal service.

Activity 1: Identifying Concerns and Needs

- What are the main concerns about aging that you would like to address?
- Are there specific areas of your physical health that you are more concerned about at this moment?
- How does your physical condition affect your daily quality of life?
- What are the physical limitations you currently experience and how do they impact your daily lives?
- What strategies have you found most effective in dealing with physical and cognitive challenges?
- Have you adopted any lifestyle changes specifically to address these concerns?
- Have you adopted any specific technology or tool to monitor or improve physical and cognitive health?
- How do you perceive the utility of technology in this respect?

Activity 2: Envisioning the Ideal Technology and Program

- Design thinking exercises for supporting discussion and hands-on defining desired functionalities and features of the ideal technology.

For those with mobility issues or subjective concerns about physical health combined with cognitive impairment, the sessions were adjusted to last 1 hour. These adjustments included shortening the duration and simplifying the exercises to encourage open discussion. This session, which also involved professionals, focused on identifying optimal user activities and gathering suggestions for enhancing the Gradior Active technology. The aim was to tailor the session to better suit their specific needs, ensuring a productive and inclusive dialogue.

Figure 6. Snapshots from the Final co-creation session (post to the small-scale testing)

Execution and Challenges

Recruitment

Selected end-users were contacted by professionals from the INTRAS Neuropsychology Clinic. These experts identified potential participants based on clinical information and neuropsychological profiles. Subsequently, a selection process was carried out according to inclusion and exclusion criteria through face-to-face interviews, where the objectives, characteristics, and participation in the study were detailed. Persons over 65 years of age with the capacity to understand and give voluntary consent to participate in a study will be included. They will be persons concerned about future mobility limitations due to a subjective physical impairment, excluding those with significant sensory impairments, inability to consent, psychiatric/neurological conditions, substance abuse or on

antipsychotic medication. Additionally, clinical and contact data, including the results of Mini-Mental tests, were collected to assess the cognitive abilities of the end-users. A concerted effort was made to inclusively involve participants from both urban and rural areas, involving the logistics of transportation to the memory clinic.

Ethics and legislation

The study was conducted following the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and good clinical practice regulations, submitting the protocol to the clinical research ethics committee for approval. All participants were provided with a document outlining their rights according to data protection laws, and they had the opportunity to discuss the informed consent with the study coordinators. Practices such as defining an ethical protocol, obtaining informed consent from participants, ensuring the privacy and security of data, and adhering to guidelines for responsible research were established.

Two separate ethical protocols were developed, one for the Co-creation sessions and submitted to the Ethics Committee, and one for the small-scale pilot activity submitted to the Regional Ethical Committee of the Implementation Area (registration / acceptance code: PI 22-2570 NO HCUV). Ultimately, the employed methodology underwent specific adjustments, and a questionnaire assessing system usability (SUS) was introduced after informing the Ethical Committee.

Outcomes and Analysis

Throughout the study, we gathered both qualitative data (from co-creation sessions and post-pilot semi-structured interviews) and quantitative data (through the previously mentioned questionnaires). The ensuing sections will detail the analysis of this qualitative feedback alongside the statistical evaluation of the quantitative data collected.

Small-Scale Pilot on Gradior Active Usability:

This study focused on the usability of the Gradior Active tool by the user, providing general data on user profiles and their physical condition, with a particular emphasis on usability evaluations.

This study aimed at assessing the Gradior Active tool's usability, focusing on users' profiles, their physical conditions, and specifically on usability evaluations. The participant group was predominantly male (74%), aged between 70 and 75 years, with the majority having completed secondary education. Results showed an improvement in the quality-of-life index (EQ-5L) post-use, particularly in those with a higher educational background. The geriatric depression scale remained unchanged, suggesting stability in emotional well-being. Activity levels, as measured by the RAPA scale, showed a minor increase in active engagement after the Gradior Active intervention, with exercises being perceived as more manageable post-session.

User experience, assessed via the UEQ scale, indicated initially positive expectations that slightly dipped over time, pinpointing potential areas for enhancement. Conversely, the SUS scale highlighted a consistently positive perception of usability, affirming the tool's ease of use and usefulness.

Feedback from semi-structured interviews identified improvement areas for Gradior Active Prototype, focusing on increasing technological autonomy to positively impact quality of life. Recommendations included making the tool more applicable to daily scenarios, enhancing its accessibility for individuals with low digital literacy, and refining instructions, virtual representations, music, and interface for better usability by those with psychomotor limitations.

Despite identified areas for enhancement, the overall feedback underlined Grador Active's potential as a therapeutic tool, suggesting that with adaptations it could significantly benefit therapeutic settings and significantly benefit users' quality of life.

Co-creation sessions:

Participants voiced concerns over cognitive and physical deterioration and a feeling of disenfranchisement in decision-making. While some were not experiencing decline, issues with physical mobility were common, alongside apprehensions about adopting technology.

Active engagement strategies mentioned included cognitive games, physiotherapy, swimming, yoga, and writing, with a preference for multidirectional, home-based technological solutions supported by professional guidance.

The study underscored the desire for a holistic and personalized approach to physical and cognitive stimulation, suggesting the integration of a vital sign monitoring device into a diversified program. The aesthetics of the virtual trainer, motivational strategies, and the scheduling of group exercises were deemed important, with a preference for interfaces akin to ALEXA highlighted.

For ideal functionalities, the need for dynamic, realistic programs that evolve and evaluate exercises to sustain interest and stimulation was emphasized. These insights are crucial for developing and refining future programs in this domain.

Conclusions

Lessons Learned

The pilot study and co-creation sessions have established a solid foundation for future developments, suggesting an innovative approach that combines artificial intelligence (AI), virtual reality (VR), and expert input to improve cognitive and physical training. The early phases of research have successfully identified user needs and preferences, setting the stage for advancements that could revolutionize service delivery in this domain.

Professional guidance emerges as a critical component, bridging the gap between technology and its practical application, thus enhancing user confidence and competence in utilizing digital health solutions. The preference for a holistic approach suggests future tools should comprehensively address both physical and cognitive health, integrating features such as vital sign monitoring to provide a rounded assessment of user well-being.

The promise of AI and VR in creating immersive therapeutic experiences points towards a significant opportunity for future research. This includes not only the exploration of these technologies but also the development of interventions that leverage their potential to deliver innovative, evidence-based care. Additionally, facilitating social connectivity through technology can amplify the therapeutic value of interventions, offering not just physical and cognitive benefits but also emotional and psychological support.

In summary, the Grador Active study highlights the significant benefits digital health technologies can offer to older adults, advocating for continued innovation and research to fully realize their potential in supporting a comprehensive approach to active and healthy aging.

Recommendations

Future research should focus on interdisciplinary collaboration to innovate and refine digital health technologies, ensuring they are both clinically effective and aligned with user needs. Longitudinal studies are essential to evaluate the long-term impacts of these interventions on health, quality of

life, and independence. Investigating the scalability of interventions and strategies to broaden access, particularly among underserved populations, will be crucial. Moreover, the exploration of emerging technologies like augmented reality and machine learning could lead to more personalized and adaptive health interventions. Finally, research into policy development and implementation strategies will be key to facilitating the broader adoption of validated technologies within healthcare systems and communities.

2.4. Case Study 4. Multidimensional Physical Fitness Testing Protocol for Aging Persons (GAIA/Spain)

Study description

Use of technology on rehabilitation and monitoring elder people.

The aim of this study is to examine the usability and benefits of the use of technology on monitoring bio parameters, rehabilitation and exercising programmes. Different starting points were considered for this study: people with cognitive problems, informal caregivers and active people using technology for supporting exercising and monitoring.

The study also involved two co-creation sessions, in which the researchers collaborated with potential users and stakeholders to design and evaluate the potential use of technology. The co-creation process consisted of two sessions, in which the participants provided feedback and suggestions on the considerations for this study. The researchers also conducted two small-scale pilot study, with the participation of elderly people.

Objectives for this study:

- Identify the potential use of technology regarding monitoring bio parameters in elderly people and the use of apps and devices for activity guidance.
- Facilitate the cooperation between technology actors and caregivers' actors.
- Identification of needs and resources.
- Needs and requirements from the point of view of final users (elderly people) regarding the use of technology and the potential activity monitoring.
- Know the level of acceptance of elderly people regarding the use of technology.

Questions to be answered:

- What is their current experience with (intervention) technology?
- To what extent is technology accepted by caregivers? (Attitude towards technology)?
- To what extent is technology accepted by elderly people? (Attitude towards technology)?
- What are the advantages and limitations of using technology?

Data collection phase 1: Co-creation (2 co-creation sections).

For the co-creation sessions the process followed were the identification of stakeholders participating in the activity, identification of places for co-creation session, collecting information from stakeholders.

Stakeholder engagement included technology companies focused on elderly monitoring, caregivers, and seniors as end users. Co-creation sessions took place at two locations: a caregiver center in Gernika and GAIA's facilities. Data were gathered through surveys and questionnaires on usability, interest, and perceptions, alongside informal methods during the pilot phase. In total, 22 participants were involved.

Figure 7. Snapshots from the Co-creation session with companies, residences and caregivers on the 28/09/2022

Figure 8. Snapshots from the Co-creation session with stakeholders on the 09/11/2022

Working aspects commented during co-creation sessions:

- Actual situation. What do they have to do and what problems do they encounter
- What do they think about presented technologies
- What are their requirements for technical solutions

Learning about the needs of the older adults or the tasks of the informal carers (NOT for the representatives of the formal care providers)

- What do they **MUST do** in an ordinary day? What is **important** for them to do but it is not necessary? What **would be nice** for them to do?
- What are **the pains and problems related to these needs/ tasks**? Do they need help/support? What others do for them? What's important for them to do but they cannot, and what would be nice for them to do but they do not do?
- To present and explain each feature.

Biometrics. – encourage open discussion on this service

- Which health parameters would be of relevance for them? Who do they want to inform?
- Are any health parameters more relevant for women, or a specific age category or for psychological care?
- Alarm button

Main findings during co-creation session:

Regarding biometrics:

During the co-creation session focused on the integration of technology in elder care, valuable insights were gathered, particularly regarding the use of biometric monitoring. Older adults and their

informal carers expressed a strong preference for monitoring vital health parameters such as oxygen levels, temperature, blood pressure, and glucose levels. The utility of pulse oximeters for tracking blood oxygen saturation was highlighted, with suggestions for recording historical oxygen level data for better health management.

The discussion also delved into the potential of smartwatches and similar devices in monitoring these biometric parameters. The convenience of having vital health information readily available without the need for additional actions, like connecting to external devices or manual record-keeping, was seen as a significant advantage. The biometrics feature of smartwatches was particularly appreciated for several reasons:

It simplifies routine health monitoring for the elderly, reducing the complexity of managing their health.

The participants noted that continuous biometric monitoring could enhance the feeling of safety and contribute to overall health maintenance.

The ability to record comprehensive health data was valued for its importance in medical assessments and in case of emergencies.

Smartwatches were considered especially beneficial over smartphones for individuals with dementia, as they are less likely to be forgotten or misplaced.

Informal carers also recognized the advantages of these technologies, noting that such solutions could save time and offer respite from their caregiving duties.

However, challenges were identified, including apprehensions about adopting new technologies among those unfamiliar with the internet, apps, or modern devices. Concerns were also raised about the privacy and security of the data collected by these devices. Learning to use the devices effectively and gaining the necessary knowledge to exploit their full potential were seen as potential obstacles.

Overall, the session underscored the critical importance of designing accessible, user-friendly technology solutions that address both the health monitoring needs and the usability concerns of older adults and their caregivers.

Usability

Another common expectation and concern for the interviewees are the friendliness and the easiness to use the apps and devices. Even if technology adoption is a cumbersome process, which often meets scepticism and anxiety among the older adults, overall, most of those who were interviewed only expressed the expectation of safeness and high usability in accordance with low abilities in using technologies. This limiting factor is addressed from the very beginning of the developmental process rather than toward the end when the system is ready for field trials.

Data collection phase 2: Small scale pilot study

Two small-scale pilots were conducted: one related to the use of technology for monitoring elderly people (bio parameters) and one related to the use of technology as support for exercising.

Pilot 1: Use of devices for monitoring parameters.

30 participants in total. The selection of participants has been carried out considering the following characteristics:

- People over 65 years of age.
- Balanced proportion of women and men.
- Institutionalized people and people living at home.

D7.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA3

To maintain the confidentiality of the results, the data collected has been anonymized and no one outside the control of pilot centre has had access to the identity of the participants in the testing sessions. Prior to carrying out the pilot, it was necessary to pass an ethical committee to validate the information collection and data processing process. To pass the ethics committee, a descriptive report was prepared for the pilots with the scope and description of the parameters collected and the information capture process.

Description of the pilot:

Use of smart devices for monitoring the frailty of the elderly in a home environment. This device monitors different vital signs, such as: (i) body temperature, (ii) heart rate, (iii) blood oxygen saturation and (iv) electrocardiogram. In addition, through an accelerometer and magnetometer system it will be possible to detect falls.

Collection of the following information:

1. Body temperature
2. Heart rate
3. Blood oxygen saturation
4. Electrocardiogram
5. Using an accelerometer and magnetometer system it will be possible to detect falls

Objectives of the pilot:

- Testing of Smartband technologies with the senior group
- Obtain data from senior study group
- Assessment of the usefulness of Smartband and the identification of common diseases in seniors.

Figure 9. Communications Diagram

Collected information some examples:

Figure 10. Electrocardiogram measurement

Figure 11. Heart Rate

Analysis of the results from the point of view of caregivers.

Complementing the piloting a survey was carried out in order to analyse the impressions of the caregivers regarding the use of technology for monitoring elderly people.

The analysis includes the results of a test aimed at consumers with the aim of analysing the interest of the B2C market in solutions such as those that the pilot 1 (Vitalise project) intends to provide.

This is a web survey aimed at 300 people aged 40 years.

Why this target? We wanted to focus the study on those people who, due to their life cycle, may be more likely to live in an environment in which cognitive deterioration may be more present.

The results of the survey showed that almost all of the people surveyed found a device useful that allows them to geolocate disoriented people and detect falls. The electronic device to remember medication intake is also perceived as useful. The system for detecting cognitive impairment generates less interest. The technologies that arouse the most interest are those for care, above those for diagnosis. 59% of the people surveyed estimate that the monthly cost of a technology that integrates all the functionalities analysed would be less than €40. Many people are aware of the privacy risks involved in certain applications, and yet they do not avoid them or even care about them.

D7.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA3

Figure 12. Perceived Utility analysis and results

Pilot 2: Using the support of technology for supporting exercising

Piloting in the use of technology for guiding exercises oriented to improve the mobility of elderly people. This pilot was made in cooperation with Actif company.

Number of participants: 9 (elder people from 75 years to 94 years)

Researchers: 2

Procedure:

- Pre-session collecting information from participants regarding physical activity and the experience in executing activity routines.
- Presentation of the application
- Following a training session
- Post-session collecting information from participants. Impressions, suggestions of improvements.

Figure 13. Snapshots from the Small-scale pilot with technology for exercising and monitoring

Analysis of the results from the point of view of final users

After the session the participants were consulted about their impressions regarding the use of this type of apps and programmes to follow a training session at home or in an elderly centre. Main findings can be summarised in the following aspects:

- They could follow the training programme without problem. The exercises were like the ones that they used to perform in a normal face to face session.
- They commented that this type of session is useful when you can't move from home (for example what happened during COVID period)
- They prefer to do this type of activity in a collective way (with more people) avoiding the sense of loneliness
- They commented that the type of exercises helps to improve mobility and promotes healthy activity that can be adapted to the user needs.
- The possibility of personalised exercises was well valued by the participants.
- Main fair was the difficulty of use this type of technology at home. They commented that perhaps they will need the support of a family to execute it.

Execution and Challenges

During the execution phase different stakeholders participated in co-creation sessions and piloting session. Apart from collecting information from the piloting phase, a concept test survey with consumers was developed analysing the interest of market for this type of devices.

The main barriers commented during the piloting phase and co-creation sessions can be summarized in the following aspects:

1. **Technology Acceptance:** One primary challenge is the acceptance of technology by elderly users. This includes concerns about usability, understandability, and the perceived utility of technology in improving their quality of life. Older individuals might be resistant to adopting new technologies due to a lack of familiarity or fear of making mistakes.
2. **Design and Usability:** Designing technology that is both accessible and easy to use for elderly individuals with varying degrees of technological literacy is a significant challenge. This includes the need for intuitive interfaces, clear instructions, and the ability to accommodate physical or cognitive impairments.
3. **Personalization and Adaptability:** The technology needs to be adaptable and customizable to meet the specific health and mobility challenges of individual users. This includes adjusting the level of exercises, monitoring specific bio parameters relevant to the user's health condition, and providing personalized feedback and recommendations.
4. **Integration with Existing Healthcare Systems:** Integrating new technologies with existing healthcare and support systems can be complex. This includes ensuring compatibility, data privacy and security, and facilitating communication between different stakeholders, such as healthcare providers, caregivers, and the individuals using the technology.
5. **Cost and Accessibility:** The cost of developing, deploying, and maintaining technology solutions can be prohibitive for some users or institutions. Ensuring that these technologies are affordable and accessible to those who need them most is a significant challenge.
6. **Data Privacy and Security:** Safeguarding the privacy and security of personal health data collected through technology is crucial. Users need to trust that their sensitive information is handled securely and in compliance with data protection regulations.
7. **Efficacy and Evidence-Based Practice:** Demonstrating the efficacy of technology-based interventions in improving health, mobility, and quality of life is essential. This requires rigorous

testing, validation, and the development of evidence-based practices to ensure that the technology delivers tangible benefits.

8. **Training and Support:** Providing adequate training and ongoing support for users and caregivers is necessary to ensure the effective use and sustainability of technology-based interventions. This includes technical support, as well as guidance on how to integrate the technology into daily routines effectively.

These challenges highlight the need for a multidisciplinary approach that incorporates user-centred design, healthcare expertise, and continuous evaluation and adaptation to ensure the successful implementation and adoption of technology for elderly care.

Outcomes and Analysis

As commented in previous phases, some surveys were executed during the co-creation and piloting phase commented different aspects related to the use of technology in monitoring parameters and do exercise. Evaluating the effectiveness of the use of technology in monitoring bio parameters and supporting exercising, involves a comprehensive methodology that encompasses both qualitative and quantitative measures. The goal is to capture the holistic impact of the program on participants' well-being, social interaction, cognitive function, and emotional health. Here's an outline of the evaluation methodology and key performance indicators (KPIs) that were considered:

Evaluation Methodology:

1. **Baseline Assessment:** Established baseline measurements for participants' health, mobility, and technology usage to compare against post-intervention outcomes.
2. **Mixed-Methods Approach:** Use both quantitative and qualitative research methods. Quantitative methods included surveys and biometric data analysis, while qualitative methods involved interviews and focus groups to gather participant feedback on their experiences.
3. **User Engagement and Satisfaction Surveys:** Evaluate participants' engagement levels and satisfaction with the technology to assess usability and acceptance.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):

1. **Health Outcomes:** Changes in specific health metrics (e.g., blood pressure, heart rate, glucose levels) monitored by the technology.
2. **Mobility Improvements:** Improvements in mobility metrics, such as gait speed, balance tests scores, and functional reach, indicating enhanced physical capabilities.
3. **Adherence to Exercise Programs:** The frequency and consistency of participants engaging in prescribed exercise routines facilitated by the technology.
4. **User Engagement:** Metrics related to how often and how interactively participants use the technology, including app logins, wearable device usage, and completion rates of health monitoring tasks.
5. **Technology Acceptance:** Participant feedback on ease of use, satisfaction, and perceived usefulness of the technology, often measured through surveys or interviews.
6. **Quality of Life:** Perception of quality of life, indicating overall well-being and satisfaction with life.
7. **Cost-Effectiveness:** Analysis of the costs associated with implementing the technology against the benefits gained, such as reduced healthcare visits, hospitalizations, or improvements in health and mobility.

Analysis

The use of technology by elderly people can be considered as a challenging item but on the contrary, some benefits were addressed by the participants in the co-creation phase and piloting phase:

1. **Improved Health Monitoring:** Technology enables continuous, real-time monitoring of vital signs and other health indicators, allowing for early detection of potential health issues and timely interventions. This can lead to better health outcomes and potentially reduce the need for hospital visits and medical interventions.
2. **Enhanced Mobility and Independence:** By supporting exercises tailored to their specific needs, technology can help elderly individuals improve their strength, balance, and overall mobility. This contributes to maintaining or enhancing their independence and quality of life.
3. **Personalized Care:** Technology allows for personalized health and exercise programs that can be adapted to the individual's current health status, progress, and preferences. This personalization can increase the effectiveness of health interventions and motivate users to engage more actively in their health management.
4. **Increased Access to Care:** Digital health technologies can provide individuals, especially those in remote or underserved areas, with greater access to healthcare services, information, and support. This can help bridge gaps in the healthcare system and ensure that more people receive the care they need.
5. **Data-Driven Insights:** The data collected through technology can provide valuable insights into the health trends of the aging population, inform the development of new health interventions, and improve the overall understanding of aging-related health issues.
6. **Support for Caregivers:** Technology can also support caregivers by providing them with tools to monitor the health and safety of their loved ones, reducing the burden and stress associated with caregiving responsibilities.
7. **Community and Social Connection:** Technologies that facilitate virtual interactions can help reduce feelings of isolation among elderly individuals by keeping them connected with their families, friends, and healthcare providers.
8. **Cost-Effectiveness:** In the long term, technology-driven interventions can be cost-effective by reducing the need for traditional healthcare services, minimizing hospital stays, and preventing health issues through early intervention.
9. **Scalability and Flexibility:** Digital health solutions can be scaled and adapted to meet the evolving needs of the aging population, providing a flexible approach to address the diverse challenges faced by elderly individuals across different settings.
10. **Empowerment:** Empowering aging individuals to take an active role in their health and well-being, technology can foster a sense of control and engagement in their health care journey, leading to better health outcomes and satisfaction.

Outcomes:

- Testing of different tools and application for bio parameters monitoring and activity exercise
- Involvement of different stakeholders in co-creation and piloting phase.

Conclusions/ lessons learned

The conclusions and lessons highlight the potential and challenges of using technology to support elderly individuals in maintaining their health and mobility. They underscore the need for careful consideration of design, usability, personalization, and integration with healthcare systems to successfully implement technology solutions in this context.

Conclusions

1. **Technology Integration Feasibility:** There is a feasible pathway for integrating technology into the care of elderly individuals to monitor health parameters and support physical activities. This can lead to improved health outcomes and enhanced quality of life.
2. **User-Centric Design is Key:** The success of technology adoption among the elderly heavily relies on user-friendly design, ease of use, and clear value in improving their daily lives. Technologies that are intuitive and tailored to the specific needs and capabilities of the elderly are more likely to be accepted and effectively used.
3. **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Effective development and implementation of such technologies require collaboration among healthcare professionals, technologists, caregivers, and the elderly themselves to ensure that the solutions meet the actual needs and preferences of users.
4. **Positive Impact on Independence and Healthcare:** The use of technology for health monitoring and exercise support has the potential to significantly enhance the independence of elderly individuals, reduce the burden on caregivers, and decrease healthcare costs through preventative care.

Lessons learned:

1. **Importance of Personalization:** Personalizing technology solutions to fit the individual needs and health conditions of elderly users is crucial for their effectiveness and adoption.
2. **Challenges in Technology Adoption:** Overcoming barriers to technology adoption, such as resistance to new technologies, limited digital literacy, and physical or cognitive impairments, requires targeted education, support, and possibly the involvement of family members or caregivers.
3. **Data Privacy and Security Concerns:** Addressing concerns about data privacy and security is essential for building trust among users and ensuring compliance with regulatory standards.
4. **Continuous Feedback and Improvement:** The development of technology solutions should be an iterative process, incorporating continuous feedback from users to refine and improve the technology.
5. **Healthcare System Integration:** Integrating technology solutions with existing healthcare systems and practices can enhance care coordination and ensure a more holistic approach to elderly care.

2.5. Case Study 4. Multidimensional Physical Fitness Testing Protocol for Aging Persons (LAUREA/Finland)

Study description

Objective and Phases: With older adults, functional independence depends heavily on level of physical fitness. Although there are lots of studies on quantifying senior's physical capacities, most of the studies use only selected number of measurements. The object of this case study was to test physical fitness testing protocol with individuals aged 65 years and older.

Laurea Activity Living Lab has a long history of cooperation with the Espoo city Exercise and sport department. The study was planned together with municipality representatives. Parties agreed that the city will reserve activity site and will recruit participants through their own channels. Laurea will organize the measurement setting, collect needed materials for that and take care of the actual measurement activity.

D7.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA3

The measurement protocol was developed and used earlier in some of the city of Espoo events. The protocol consisted of 12 different tests that look physical fitness level from different perspectives: endurance, strength, agility, flexibility, balance, and body composition. All selected tests were safe, easy to administrate, feasible to this age group, had previous reference values and have proved to be valid and reliable measures. However, there is not available such a protocol with this type of combination.

The activity began from Laurea's perspective by designing the contents of the measurements and obtaining ethical approval from the local Research Ethical board. One class of physiotherapy students (approximately 40 students) was informed about and educated on the measurement protocol as part of one study unit. Meanwhile Espoo city reserved needed space from local sport hall and started recruitment activities through their own channels. Espoo city also recruited a class of students from secondary level school to help to organize event in practice (guiding, keeping cloakroom etc.).

In addition to the measurement event, a plan to recruit participants for physical activity measurements were done. This was also included to the research ethical approval process. The idea of measuring the activity for selected group of participants was to understand the behaviour that has yielded to physical fitness level they have. For this, participants were asked to wear physical activity tracker (Sensewear armband) for 24 hours and keep diary of their physical activity doings.

The testing facility was organized so that there were multiple operating points where the measurements took place. Participants circled around all points. The very last point was a place where they would hand over the score sheet (two equal ones were written, the other one was kept by the participants) and hear some interpretation of the test results. At this point few volunteers were asked to participate to the physical activity tracker study. Also, a feedback form and the short version of the "User Experience Questionnaire, UEQ" were asked to fill. Laurea provided some reference values to Espoo city who transferred those to their www-pages for participant to view later. See in picture 1. the flow of the measurements.

Figure 14. Picture of the Senior physical fitness measurement day at Espoo

To provide enough measurement sessions two equal days were arranged. Espoo city arranged mandatory advance registration for the participants. Participants were organized in groups, approximately 20 persons per group. Each group's starting time was every half hour. A lunch break was kept in the middle of the day.

Execution and Challenges

Progress and Barriers: 383 participants, 118 males and 265 females, were measured. The average age was 72 years (60-88 years). There were no problems with the execution. The event went by smoothly and the feedback of the participants was very good. Some minor complaints (e.g. difficulties changing reserved time) were reported on the feedback, but that is quite normal in an event with this magnitude.

29 participants were invited to the physical fitness tracker measurement. 25 participants were measured. The measurement was organized in such a way that a person from Laurea Activity Living Lab contacted the participant who had left his/her contact details and agreed on how to supply the physical fitness tracker. Normally this happened so, that LL person took the device to participant's home and got the device back the same way.

Also, it was estimated that the majority of the participants were in good physical condition. This proved to be correct after seeing the results and comparing them to the existing reference values. To confirm this, Laurea arranged an additional measurement week on a municipality senior service centre. This is a place where seniors can spend the day by seeing each other, doing all kind of activities and participating to the organized activities. We know that seniors that use these services are generally not as fit as the ones that participated to the measurement event. 38 measurements (10 male, 28 female) were done during the week. The measurements we carried out by physiotherapy students who did their one-week training period on the place.

Organizing such a measurement event requires significant effort. Without the involvement of students and the city of Espoo, collecting this amount of data would have taken a long time. Additionally, distributing the physical activity trackers to the participants also required considerable time, as the participants lived across the city area.

Outcomes and Analysis

Evaluation and KPIs: The protocol seemed to be easy to execute. It took about half an hour for each participant to through all measurements. The length of some measurement could be calculated in seconds whereas some measurements took minutes. It is impossible or makes no sense to build up a protocol where all measurements would last about the same time. Participants were aware of this and understood some queuing at some measurement points. But the protocol could have also seen as a social happening at this age group. People met persons with same age and had a chat while circling from point to another.

The students who conducted the measurements were first-year students. This was their first-time encountering individuals as clients during their studies, making the event very useful for them in gaining practical experience. However, due to their lack of previous experience with real-life measurements, there could have been some impact on the results. As they gained more experience over time, this may have caused some instability in the results. However, upon reviewing the collected results, it is not possible to determine if such effects occurred.

From the participants' perspective, this event provided an opportunity that they seldom have. Currently, there are no places, at least locally, where individuals can go and have their physical fitness level measured. The city of Espoo advertised this event carefully, yet it was fully booked, indicating a high demand for such services. While the city can provide this service once a year, many participants expressed a desire for measurements to be available twice a year.

Collecting activity data poses even greater challenges for the municipality. Activity trackers are relatively expensive, and the budget determines the number of trackers available. Additionally, governing the process delivering and retrieving the trackers, addressing technical issues, analysing data, and providing feedback requires significant time and effort. While it would be beneficial to understand the activity levels of citizens to organize activities accordingly, this is hardly a realistic approach for the municipality to undertake. Even in Espoo, at the end of 2022, there were over 46 000 (15,1%) persons 65 years or older.

A User Experience (UX) Questionnaire (UEQ) short version was used gather feedback and insights from users about their experience with a measurement day. UEQ measures pragmatic quality via four variables and hedonic quality also via four variables. UEQ tool provides benchmarking data for full UEQ. However, tool authors argue that the short version is a reasonably good approximation of the corresponding values of the full version, thus it is possible to use benchmarks also for short version. The benchmark data allows conclusions about the relative quality of the evaluated product compared to other products. Van Westendorp's Price Sensitivity Meter was used to conduct price sensitivity analysis. It includes four questions about the price levels at which respondent perceive a product to be too expensive, expensive/on the high side, cheap/good value, or too cheap. Furthermore, the following questions using 5-point Likert-scales were also asked from the participants:

- How important is it to you to measure your physical fitness level? (importance)
- How often would you be interested in measuring your physical fitness level? (interest)
- I intend to recommend today's physical fitness level measurement service, for example, to my friends, relatives, or if someone asks me for advice. (recommendation)
- If today's physical fitness level service had a cost, would I attend again next year? (cost)

The projects KPIs were:

- 200-400 participants to the measurement event
- 40 physical activity trackers to the participant
- 50 participants from the senior service centre

Analysis: Project KPIs were met quite well. 383 participants were measured during the senior measurement days. Initially all the available measurement times were reserved (over 400), but there were some cancellations and that drop the participant number under 400.

29 participants were invited to the Armband measurements to track physical activity. At the end 25 measurements were done. This was enough at the time as the data collection was quite time consuming. First of all, the LL personnel needed to agree with every person about the suitable timetables for delivering, wearing and pick up the activity tracker. As there were participants from around the city of Espoo, this took quite a bit agreements and efforts. There were some thoughts to repeat the measurements during the summertime (more outside activity), but the idea was rejected due to the schedule limitations.

Measurements at the Espoo keskus Senior Centre took place within one week of a student work-life training session. The students had participated in the initial measurements during the senior measurement days. A total of 38 senior centre clients were measured, which can be considered a reasonable number. Due to environmental limitations, a couple of tests were not conducted at the centre. The tests revealed what was anticipated: individuals attending the actual measurement days were in far better shape than the clients at the senior housing centre. However, both of these groups live independently at home.

About half of the physical tests conducted were those introduced by Rikli and Jones (2001) with reference values. These age-based reference values are derived from the normal population. Individuals participating in the Espoo measurement event significantly exceeded these values. For example, in the 2.5m Timed Up-and-Go test, both men and women achieved results on average that would place them in the top fifth (20%) level according to Rikli & Jones' data. On the other hand, participants from the senior centre scored results that puts them in the last quartile to the Rikli & Jones's data on average. The same phenomenon could be seen practically in every test.

According to UEQ analysis (N=378-390 depending on variable) pragmatic (mean = 2.24), hedonic (1.74) and overall (2.00) quality was excellent comparing to benchmarks. As a result, we can conclude that measurement day was well received by the participants. The reasons for participation were curiosity to know about one's own health and fitness levels, interest in tracking changes over time, recommendations from friends or colleagues, concerns about the impact of age on physical condition, and a desire for personalized information to guide fitness improvement efforts. The mean value for the perceived importance was 4.36 (4 = important, 5= Very important), for the interest it was 3.08 (3= Once a year, 4 = 2-3 times a year), for the recommendation 4.71 (4 = Somewhat agree, 5 = Completely agree) and for the cost 3.61 (3= Neither agree nor disagree, 4= Somewhat agree). The price sensitivity analysis revealed that correct pricing for measurement day would be between 16-27€, with optimum around 23€.

Conclusions

Recommendations and Lessons Learned: In today's world where governments and individuals aim for people to be independent and live in their own homes, understanding the physical fitness levels of senior citizens becomes crucial. Only by understanding these levels can proper services and aids be provided. However, currently, this understanding is lacking. There are numerous reasons behind this. From our Living Lab perspective, the biggest barriers include the lack of knowledge and skills to organize such events and protocols, to analyse the results, and, more importantly, to incorporate all this into daily practice.

As there are a great demand for this kind of services, LL could either provide such services or help to establish new service providers. Physical fitness testing is commercially available for working age individuals, but not for seniors for some reason. One common phenomenon to all age groups is that persons with good condition and health are the ones who are most likely participating to the physical fitness testing events or possibilities. There might be a reason to think how to tempt persons with decreased physical fitness levels into these tests as they would probably benefit the most. One option is the way that we acted here. Take the tests and testing facilities to the places were more sedentary people meet and spend their time.

Physical fitness testing protocol was easy to administrate and gave useful data. However, to understand individual's coping skills at the home environment some other testing should be incorporated into physical fitness tests. For example, memory problems or problems with alcohol abuse can cause diverse problems. So, to understand the situation, individually tailored tests are often also needed.

Currently the services provided for the senior citizens and especially in the field of exercise are not need-based. They are services that have been offered for years. To develop services more all kind of data is needed. LLs and schools can be useful partners to the municipalities to develop practices.

2.6. Case Study 4. Multidimensional Physical Fitness Testing Protocol for Aging Persons (TREBAG/Hungary)

Study description

Regular physical activity has a positive impact on physical and mental health (Hamilton and Neville, 2012). However, the propensity to exercise once a week decreases significantly with age, with 46% of 25–39-year-olds exercising at least once a week compared to 30% of 55+ year olds (Eurobarometer, 2018). However, it is even more important for the older age group to incorporate physical activity into their daily lives to maintain their health. Nordic walking (NW) as a leisure and rehabilitation activity has many positive effects (Roy et al, 2020; Nagyova, et al., 2020), but there is little information on how motivation and physical performance changes when the target group uses smart devices. Our aim was to investigate the impact of a 9-week NW intervention in a group of older women.

The study included 23 adult women with a mean age of 72.6 years (BMI 28.5±4.1 kg/m²), members of an older adult dance group.

Data collection took place in 4 various parts:

1. Co-creation sessions
2. Pre-testing
3. Intervention
4. Post testing

1. Co-creation sessions

The interventions were preceded by a co-creation session where practitioners of older adults (care-givers, facilitators, social carers) gathered and gave their views about older adults' habits on the use of smart devices in everyday life and specifically in relation to movement and physical fitness. Also, older adults were gathered to get information about the forthcoming programme and to gain their insights into possible challenges and fears as well as expectations.

At the beginning and end of the programme, the participants took an internationally validated physical fitness test specifically designed for older people (Senior Fitness Test, Rikli & Jones, 1999), which provided information on their current fitness status. Their well-being status was assessed using the WHO Well-being Questionnaire, also validated and their motivational level by the CPAS validated test. After 9 weeks (2x1.5 hours per week) of Nordic walking training, the above measurements were repeated. Participants received a smart armband (AMAZFIT Band 7) and were instructed to its usage. They were asked to wear the device during the interventions.

The **main objectives** of the co-creation sessions were:

- To identify challenges, potentials in maintaining and improving physical fitness, health and wellbeing of older people using outdoor spaces
 - To identify the tendencies and willingness of older people to use smart tools in their everyday activities

2. Pre-testing

Pre-testing of participants happened during one day in a community centre in Budapest. Previously interested participants were gathered and were informed about the proposed programme, its steps and requirements. Those who showed interested and did not have the exclusion criteria (severe health problems) got a smart wearable and could join the tests.

Altogether 23 participants took part in the pre-measurement phase.

The study was conducted following the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and in line with the submitted and approved protocol to the research ethics committee of ELTE. All participants were provided with a document outlining their rights according to data protection laws, and they had the opportunity to discuss the informed consent with the study coordinators. Practices such as defining an ethical protocol, obtaining informed consent from participants, ensuring the privacy and security of data, and adhering to guidelines for responsible research were established.

During the pre-test time the following tools were used, and parameters were measured

- Healthy Lifestyle Questionnaire (HLQ)
- IPaQ-7 Questionnaire
- CPAS
- WHOQOL
- Senior Fitness Test 1: Aerobic Capacity Assessment
- Senior Fitness Test 2: Upper Limb Flexibility Assessment
- Senior Fitness Test 3: Lower Limb Flexibility Assessment
- Senior Fitness Test 4-5: Strength-Endurance Assessment
- Senior Fitness Test 6: Agility Assessment
- TANITA Bioimpedancimeter: Body Composition, Bioimpedance Analysis

3. Intervention

The intervention was preceded by an information day where participants got information about the project, were informed about the programme and got a short introduction into the use of the chosen smart device.

Also, at a next occasion they signed the required consent and other documents, filled in questionnaires (see above) and did the stations of the senior fitness test.

The Nordic walking intervention was conducted by a trained trainer of Nordic walking and physical education. It took nine weeks from June to September and trainees met twice a week for approximately 90 mins per occasion.

Each training started with a warmup session, followed by a tailor-made walking session and closed by a stretching session. Also, each time the use of smart wearables was required. The smart bands were activated to measure and record the given session and were used during the walk to monitor parameters of heartbeat and steps. Each participant could follow their performance. Besides the use of the smart band, participants were also instructed on the technical basis of Nordic walking. The nine-week session was not only a fitness training but also a learning pathway in understanding digital tools and learning the basics of a new physical activity.

Extra information as well as challenges, their possible solutions, technical and logistical information, motivational support were shared in a common FB group created specifically for the programme and shared between participants and the trainer. The FB group helped participants to encourage each other, share memories, give and get advice, get instructed and helped by the facilitator. All participants were digitally acquainted in a way that they had an email account and could use FB.

However, the use of the smart band was new to them and to most of them it was a challenge.

Real-time participation was a requirement for all participants. If someone for some reasons (health issues etc) missed a session, they were required to make it up on their own in the same week,

documenting their activities by writing a diary about their venue, steps taken, time spent and share it with the trainer. Those who failed to meet these requirements dropped out of the programme.

4. Post measurement

After the 9-week intervention the same tests were taken as in the pre-test.

To establish the similar environment, the same venue was rented for the measurement and the same conditions were established.

Execution and Challenges

Challenges:

Co-creation:

It was difficult to make participants speak out, but after a time they started to get communicative and contributed to the session.

Pre and post-tests:

Were assessed 23 female participants, with an average age of 72.6 years, covering various activities including tests completion, measuring body composition carrying out the various stations or the Senior fitness test. These required attention, time and energy both from participants and from facilitators. Organizing the event hinged on meticulous organization - arranging assistance, how to arrange locations of various testing functions on the venue, how to do timing was crucial for the successful execution. Also, facilitators needed to be instructed and informed on how the tests should be executed and how to help participants. Overall, the events went well, there were only slight problems with the execution. These included the waiting time between stations and the weather conditions for the outdoor part of the fitness test. The overall feedback of the participants was good.

Intervention:

The nine-week training of Nordic walking took place in the summertime, between the end of June and the beginning of September. Therefore, for the weather conditions a lot of challenges from extreme heat to rain showers needed to be faced. For some people this caused health related concerns. Also, this time-period was co-inciding with annual holidays for both the participating individuals and their families which sometimes hindered either the actual participation or the motivation to participate.

The novelty of the programme was two-fold for participants: they had to learn a new way of movement (Nordic walking) as well as the use of a digital tool (smart band). These were challenges which caused a lot of work to overcome on behalf of the trainer. Extra sessions as well as explanations on FB needed to be incorporated to the programme.

Outcomes and Analysis

Evaluation and KPIs: The programme had a complex protocol, consisting of many parts. Very energy and time-consuming. The co-creation session needed a long recruitment period to find the right people to ask who were willing to participate and were interested. The tests and the interventions also included organization, monitoring and follow up. The documentation was also very demanding especially in terms of human resources the whole programme was very costly.

Once the organizational aspects were over, the execution of both the co-creation sessions and the tests went smoothly. The co-creation session took about 1,5 hours and the tests altogether took

about 3-4 hours altogether to execute. The intervention was the biggest investment 1,5.2 hours twice a week plus online communication with participants.

The following KPI s were set:

Sample:

- 50 participants to be recruited to the measurement event
- 20 participants to finalise both tests
- 20 physical activity trackers to the participant

Intervention:

- Min. 8-week intervention of Nordic walking- twice a week
- Min. 20 participants completing the intervention
- Participants can use the fitness monitoring functions of the smartband by the end of the training
- Participants learn the basics of Nordic walking
- Participants feel motivated to go on with the use of smart tools

All the above KPIs were fulfilled.

Conclusions

In conclusion of the **co-creation session**, with the typical sports and forms of maintaining fitness outdoors, the participants listed the most common ones, like walking, hiking, biking. They did not have a lot of insights to examples for abroad, nor were familiar with more modern or innovative ways of fitness tools, devices, facilities. Therefore, they could not provide a very vivid and new forecast for the future. It seemed that these professionals who will be multipliers for the older generation it is also needed to get more information on fitness/health/wellbeing and the modern devices.

Participants agreed that in Hungary still the traditional ways of maintaining wellbeing and fitness rules in the older generation. The training of professionals, health care workers, facilitators on the first hand and the end users on the other hand are strongly needed to use and apply more modern technological tools and solutions in the sector.

As for the **tests and the intervention** both required a lot of staff effort to organize and conduct, especially the 9-week Nordic walking training. However, it can be claimed that it was worth the effort, as the team was enjoying the gatherings, they got an insight into their physical fitness, learnt about new technology, about a new form of sport and this seems to be sustainable too as most of them even after months of the intervention still use the smart wearables.

In the research point of view the whole programme collected a lot of data. Some of these are already concluded, but most of them is a very rich pool of data for future analysis.

In the Living Lab point of view, this pilot project has proved that this age group is capable of learning new digital technologies combined with learning of new types of movement and can give meaningful user experience insight on the products and the services. Their continuous involvement both via co-creation and via feedback and monitoring is crucial to keep them motivated and engaged.

2.7. Case Study 5. Characterizing the Interaction of the Effects of a Museum Visit on Mobility, Cognition, and Well-being in People with Stroke (McGill-CRIR/Canada)

Study description

The overall aim of the MOB and NEURO-MBAM projects was to determine the feasibility of carrying out an ecological study at the Montreal Museum of Fine Arts (MBAM), by evaluating various aspects ranging from participant recruitment to the satisfaction of the various players involved. In other words, the aim was to explore the feasibility of deploying a fleet of equipment and technological instruments to measure and document enough valid data on mobility and cognition during a museum experience. The objectives were to:

- 1) Document the ability to recruit healthy and acquired brain injury (ABI) participants and compare their characteristics to those in the protocol.
- 2) To document aspects related to experimental methods and procedures, the choice of outcome measures used, and in-study adjustments to improve them.
- 3) Assess the acceptance and suitability of the study for the various stakeholders (visitors participating in the sub-projects, museum managers and researchers).
- 4) Assess human, material and financial resources and capacity to manage and carry out the study.
- 5) Analyse the data generated by the sub-projects to assess their validity, the achievement of objectives and their relevance to informing the various stakeholders (visitors, researchers and museum managers) about relevant aspects of mobility at the museum.

Prior to data collection, two ethic approvals were obtained from the CCSMTL's Comité d'éthique de la recherche en réadaptation et en déficience physique. Recognition was also obtained from the Université de Montréal (UdeM) ethics committee. The latter allows access to a portion of the funding obtained and managed at UdeM. Written informed consent was obtained from each participant. Participants were free to withdraw from the research project at any time, without explanation, but none did so.

Execution and Challenges

The data collections were carried out on December 3, 2019, and over eight days in 2021 and 2022. From a total of 153 participants, 17 participants were recruited for the control group and 19 participants were recruited for the stroke group, five (5) of whom had aphasia, highlighting the significant challenges of recruiting a neurological population.

Figure 15. Interaction with the expositions involved in the study in the Montreal Museum of Fine Arts (MBAM)

- (i) A knowledge transfer day was held on February 22, 2023, at the MBAM cinema, where researchers presented their research results to participants in the collections and to MBAM members and managers. Following this day of exchange, MBAM members shared their experiences with our research teams, both for the MOB and NEURO projects. The reflections and challenges that emerged from these exchanges are presented below.
- (ii) It is possible to move technological equipment to the MBAM. However, some adaptations to the scenario, the reception arrangements and the duration of the activities need to be considered.
- (iii) Additional human resources are needed to manage the circulation of equipment. The circulation of equipment brings its own set of difficulties: providing a specific entrance door, reserving a specific area for depositing and installing equipment, additional security guards.
- (iv) On the part of researchers, it is important to come and see the site before developing experimental protocols. A pre-visit is essential. After the visit, the research group must propose a precise route and protocol for approval.
- (v) There are many constraints: for example, no tables in the rooms, no chairs, no collages on the walls. Equipment cannot be installed in areas where the general public or schoolchildren can circulate. In short, you must not interfere with the normal running of the museum.
- (vi) It must be accepted that other visitors are in the room, talking and viewing the works at the same time. It's essential to work within the museum's normal opening hours.
- (vii) Bear in mind that works of art are subject to rotation and may disappear from the exhibition rooms to be replaced by others.
- (viii) To accept a request for data collection, the MBAM requires at least two months' notice, either to reserve rooms, for technical specifications, security needs, the need for mediators or guides, etc.
- (ix) It would be relevant to involve museum staff in the problematization and to make links with their knowledge of museology. Questions were raised about the choice of works and the reasons for choosing them. It would have been ideal to work in co-creation for more valuable data and with a view to raising awareness of the museum world.
- (x) For the future, consider multi/transdisciplinary research plans to better investigate research objects. Gain a better understanding of the MBAM's current practices so as to be able to make more relevant proposals.
- (xi) It is possible to integrate people with disabilities or special needs; this is done on a daily basis at the museum. This is not a problem, as long as there is supervision. The research team must take care of their special needs.

- (xii) December 3 was a demanding day, but the two 4-day blocks were fine, with the opening hours respected. However, headphones, stickers on the wall and the need for silence to hear the audio experience disrupted activities.
- (xiii) The results can be used to better define the MBAM's research directions and needs. The results on rehabilitation are very interesting.

Outcomes and Analysis

Characterizing the mobility of MBAM visitors

Two studies were carried out, involving two groups of healthy elderly people (n=20; n=13) and a group of post-stroke people (n=15) who could walk independently with technical aids.

The researchers evaluated the effects of a museum visit on the locomotor abilities and physical behaviours of healthy and post-stroke elderly people. Locomotor abilities before and after a 45-60 min museum visit were assessed using standardized tests (5 m walk at natural and fast speed, stair climbing and chair lifting repeated five times) and an instrumented treadmill (GAITRite system). Initial statistical analyses (parametric and non-parametric) revealed, prior to the visit, an expected significant reduction in the locomotor abilities of post-stroke individuals compared to healthy individuals (mean 50.2%; ranging from 33.1% to 95.6%). For both groups, test performance was not reduced after the visit; rather, an improving trend was observed. These results indicate that a museum visit of this duration seems to be very well tolerated and managed by post-stroke individuals, with no negative consequences on their locomotor performance. These initial results will be supplemented by further observations and data for an overall analysis of the museum visit effects.

All planned participants took part in the study, and eligibility criteria were adequate. The procedures were deemed feasible for the pre-tests, but a few people left before the post-tests. A few modifications were made during the course of the study, and some tests were abandoned (walking test). Some tasks were also adapted due to the lack of fluidity between stations (didn't know what to do between stations), and it would have been good to have companions. It would have been preferable to have one more member of the research team, especially for the clinical tests.

Sometimes, the groups of children interrupted the team and the experiments. Examination of the quantitative data shows that the study has a good chance of success, but the participants did not provide any qualitative information. The researchers are confident that the technologies used will deliver the desired results. If they were to do it all over again, they would add an additional person to the team and allow for more time.

Characterization and quantification of mobility and fatigue associated with a museum visit experience at the MBAM among people aged 50 and over.

Twenty-five people participated, and the target number was 40. Eligibility criteria were deemed adequate. Eligibility and selection criteria were deemed very adequate and not at all restrictive.

The procedures were feasible, although some changes had to be made. The intake questionnaires were considered too long (participant fatigue). The experiments were not considered a burden by either participants or researchers. The team would have needed more human resources. The researchers are confident that the data will provide the expected results. There was no loss of data.

The collection procedures were deemed highly feasible and appropriate for achieving the objectives, and no modifications or adjustments were required (a museum map would have been necessary). All participants understood the questions and procedures very well, no participant withdrew during

the study, and they completed all tasks, and it was not an inconvenience for them. It was an "average" burden for the research team, but no breakdowns or adverse effects occurred.

The data collected was of high quality, and the procedures/technologies were appropriate for the clientele. The team had enough resources.

Characterizing the psychological and neurocognitive effects of a museum visit

Researchers assessed the brain activity evoked during a free museum visit and associated it with psychological well-being. The engagement of the ventrolateral prefrontal regions of 18 participants aged 65 to 79 were studied using near-infrared spectroscopy. The results show that the more attentional processes are engaged, the more the visitor's perceived anxiety after a museum visit decreases. 50% of participants reported a reduction in anxiety. Engaging the attentional processes involved in focusing and processing the work of art, its form and meaning, is essential for a museum visit to have a positive impact on psychological well-being.

Eligibility criteria were adequate and collection procedures were feasible (no changes necessary). The procedures worked well and were appropriate for the clientele.

The participants completed the task well, except for one person who ran out of time. The team was well prepared, so the procedure was not a burden. In addition, human and material resources were adequate. The fact that we had one hour's access to the spaces before the start of the gave enough time for preparation. At the time of the interview, the researchers did not know whether the data would be valid, but they were confident. They did not receive any feedback from the participants. If they were to do it again, they would appreciate a quieter visit and no school visits at the same time.

Measures of feasibility and satisfaction of participants and visit experiences

Experiential experience

The researchers wanted to understand aspects of the lived experience in relation to the participants' perspective and the characteristics of the interior environment, in addition to observing and documenting their interactions with the research projects and museum spaces. The team studied four participants and, using a modified version of the EQST tool, carried out a hermeneutic, content, and comparative analysis of the visual and documented data. It was observed that most participants took advantage of the benches as soon as they arrived, regardless of their age. Regarding interior design, some signs are difficult to read due to light glare obscuring the text. In addition, lighting conditions are uneven throughout the gallery. These results provide a better understanding of the relationship between space and the museum experience and will enable adjustments to be made.

Cognition, fatigue, anxiety and well-being

The team recruited a total of 48 participants. 12 participants did not attend. As a result, 36 participants were evaluated. The researchers' objective was to assess the impact of a museum visit on psychological health and well-being, as well as to determine the feasibility of such a study. A total of 19 post-stroke elderly participants and 17 healthy elderly participants were evaluated.

Results showed neurocognitive differences between the two groups in verbal learning, immediate memory, working memory, mental flexibility, and selective attention. However, despite the cognitive differences, there were no other significant differences between the groups regarding pre- and post-visit psychological health. In all participants, there were no significant differences on any measure, but trends were observable post-visit, namely a slight increase in well-being and fatigue, as well as a slight decrease in anxiety, stress, and pain.

Feasibility

D7.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA3

As this was a feasibility study, participants completed at the end of the evaluation a 10-item satisfaction and feasibility questionnaire, featuring eight 5-point Likert scale questions ranging from "not at all" to "very much," and two "yes" or "no" questions, followed by a final comments section.

Figure 16. Graphical representation of satisfaction and feasibility results

In short, the study is feasible, and a high level of satisfaction has been obtained from the participants. This interest and satisfaction were clearly expressed by three participants who were invited to share their experiences on the day of February 22, 2023. The participants also mentioned the importance of carrying out such experiments in a culturally rich environment such as a museum. They also

expressed their appreciation for a knowledge transfer activity where they are invited to learn about the results of the research in which they have participated.

Comparison of comprehension of an adapted vs. non-adapted description of an audio work of art in healthy elderly and stroke patients.

The overall aim of the team was to improve linguistic accessibility of information at the Montréal Museum of Fine Arts (MMFA) for all, especially for persons with language and communication limitations. To this end, three exhibits were chosen for which audio guides were created. Each exhibit was accompanied by two audio guides, one representing the existing written MMFA text accompanying the exhibit and a second one that was linguistically simplified (e.g. short and simple sentences, frequent and simple words) using on-line tools and psycholinguistic principles of language processing. 15 participants were recruited, 10 healthy elderly and five post-stroke individuals with mild aphasia participated in this study. Each participant viewed all three exhibits listening to the audio guides, the original and the simplified, wearing eye-tracking glasses (Pupil Labs) that tracked participants' attention to details mentioned in the audio guides as they listened.

A survey of participant responses to the modified audio guides compared to the original was collected using aphasia-friendly questionnaires. Results show that persons with aphasia and most healthy aging controls preferred the modified versions of the audio guides due to the format and content.

Among people without language difficulties, level of education was a factor that determined the type of audio guide (original or modified) preferred.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the results of the MOB and NEURO MBAM preliminary studies show that it is possible and feasible to use technological equipment to collect data in museum spaces. What's more, it is possible to invite people with disabilities, such as acquired brain injury, to carry out tests using technological equipment.

On the other hand, despite the demonstrated feasibility, several obstacles were encountered by the researchers during the collection process. Challenges related to the transportation of technological equipment, limitations linked to the use of spaces, access to works of art, noise, and the museum's many visitors were cited by the researchers. In addition, recruiting the population with ABI during the COVID-19 pandemic represented a major challenge, as detailed above. Nevertheless, the researchers were able to use the technology in the museum and collect valid preliminary data.

Interestingly, both healthy elderly participants and those who had undergone an ABI expressed their satisfaction at participating in a technological experience at the museum, and all felt safe during their visit.

Finally, the MBAM partners also agree that it is possible to collect data from technological equipment in their environment, but some adjustments will be needed to optimize collection experiences.

Overall, this project has helped to develop new knowledge and, thanks to the collection of preliminary data, has been essential in guiding future research projects in public spaces such as museums. It has also helped create a critical mass of researchers and helped train the next generation. Numerous knowledge transfer activities were carried out as part of this project, to encourage the application of this methodology to other public environments or places, and to other clinical populations. Next, the data will be pooled to create a larger database for analysis, and to better understand the extent to which the idea can be transposed to different countries and cultures.

Finally, this project has promoted the integration of healthy elderly people with persons with ABI into cultural organizations such as museums, through a better understanding of the mechanisms inherent in participants and environmental barriers. The results of these preliminary studies will serve as a foundation for the development of future research projects using technology in an ecological environment, such as a museum, as well as for the development of technological interventions to improve motor skills, cognition and well-being for people with physical disabilities.

2.8. Case Study 5. Characterizing the Interaction of the Effects of a Museum Visit on Mobility, Cognition, and Well-being in People with Stroke (AUTH/Greece)

Study description

Project overview-objectives: This exploratory small case study operated by AUTH is a collaborative study between AUTH and McGill-CRIR-Canada, and for this reason it followed and replicated part of the protocol of the Canadian VITALISE partners described above. The aim of this particular small-case study was to investigate the interaction of the effects of a museum visit on mobility, cognition, well-being and the experience of individuals, as well as to investigate whether cognitively and verbally accessible audio guides of exhibits contribute to a better understanding of the descriptions of these exhibits, through measurements made using advanced technologies. Regarding the targeted participants, the aim was to include ten (10) post-stroke patients, four (4) of whom with mild to moderate aphasia, and ten (10) healthy individuals, all of them between 55 and 85 years of age (mean age of the recruited participants 68 years old). In this context, the data collected aimed also to draw some conclusions regarding the feasibility and user satisfaction of conducting a range of different measurements and interventions in a museum setting.

Shortly before the start of the study, it was considered essential to modify the original protocol (the one included in the submitted research protocol for JRA3) in certain respects, such as replacing the two visits with one, to reduce the risk of potential drop-outs, and focusing/elaborating more on the part of the audio guide comprehension.

The protocol of the study has received approval from the AUTH Ethical Committee and all the participants signed an informed consent prior to the beginning of the co-creation sessions and pilots. Participation in the study was voluntary and the participants could withdraw at any time without justification and without consequences.

Co-creation sessions: The first phase of the study included two co-creation sessions in June and September 2022, in the Museum of Casts and Antiquities in Thessaloniki, Greece, with twelve (12) participants in total, aged between 60-85 years old from the ThessAHALL Collaboration & Research Community for Independent Living. The purpose of these co-creation sessions was to explore participants' museum experience, challenges and needs or expectations, including aspects regarding the use of different technologies during the museum visits.

Figure 17. Snapshots from the co-creation sessions in the museum

Piloting phase: The piloting phase began in May 2023 and was concluded at the end of the year. Prior to the museum visit, the participants were administered some questionnaires, aiming to obtain a holistic view on their cognitive status, as well as dimensions of their physical and mental wellbeing and quality of life.

The measurements and questionnaires that used for assessing are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Measurements and questionnaires included in the protocol

Cognitive status	Mental wellbeing/Quality of life	Physical status
Montreal Cognitive Assessment	Geriatric Depression Scale	10 Metre Walk Test
Mini-Mental State Examination	Visual Analog Scale-Pain	Tinetti-test
Hopkins Verbal Learning Test	Visual Analog Scale-Stress	Berg Balance Scale
Stroop Test	Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale	30" Chair Stand Test
Trail Making A + B	EQ-5D-5L	Timed Up & Go – TUG
Digit span Forward and Backward	State-Trait Anxiety Inventory	2 Minute Walk Test
	Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory	Balance on one leg

Afterwards, the participants, one at a time, entered the museum with the members from the project's research team, where they were asked to wear some specific equipment. In particular, they initially wore a pair of smart insoles (Digitsole Pro Smart Insoles) and a smart watch (Smartwatch-Fitbit Charge 5) and were asked to walk at their own pace following a predetermined guided tour route through the museum spaces and exhibits. Breaks were provided whenever requested by the participants.

After completing their guided tour in the museum, they were asked to wear eye-tracking glasses (Pupil Labs) and headphones to listen to audio descriptions (audio guides) of three selected exhibits, the Tombstone, the Hermes of Praxiteles and the West Pediment from the temple of Zeus at Olympia. Specifically, they were asked to stand in front of three (3) exhibits and listen to the description. For each of the three exhibits, participants first listened to their original description (a description that someone can usually find next to the exhibit or in a relevant educational textbook) and then they listened to the modified, accessible version of the exhibit description (with simpler words, shorter sentences etc.). After each audio description (original and modified), they were asked to answer a number of predetermined questions related to the audio description they had just heard.

At the end, after the aforementioned equipment was removed, they were asked to answer a number of questions and questionnaires about their overall museum experience and potential challenges or stress experienced (Satisfaction and feasibility questionnaire, Visual Analog Stress scale, State-Trait Anxiety Inventory).

Figure 18. Snapshots from the piloting phase

Execution and Challenges

Overall, the pilots were conducted without major issues, showing that it is possible and feasible to use technological equipment to collect data in museum spaces. However, there were some difficulties that were encountered and have been considered for possible similar endeavours in the future. The reflections and challenges that emerged during the execution of the pilot phase are summarized below.

- Difficulties were encountered in recruiting post-stroke participants (including those with mild aphasia symptoms) through collaborating physicians and hospitals. This was the main reason why the recruited number of participants was lower than the targeted number.
- Restrictions on access to the Museum of Casts and Antiquities. Specifically, in order to visit the specific museum for the pilots, there is the need to reserve the room some days in advance, provided that no class is scheduled for the university students. In addition, during the last 2-3 months of the period when the pilots were scheduled, the Department of History and Archaeology of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, where the museum is located, was under student occupation, which prevented access to the members of the research team. In addition, there were some difficulties in accessing the museum, as there are several stairs leading to the main exhibition hall of the museum, and this was potentially a challenge for people with mobility problems.
- Challenges were also encountered with the collection of data from the eye-tracking glasses. Specifically, a smartphone with an app that was much older than the version used on computers was used to record data from the pupil core device that resulted in several differences in terms of calibration.

Outcomes and Analysis

Results from the analysis of the co-creation sessions: The results from the two co-creation sessions conducted were analysed using qualitative content analysis. All participants mentioned that they had very good experiences in previous museum visits. Acquiring new knowledge was the most motivating factor for visiting a museum (“The knowledge I can earn... however, the repetitive visits to a museum are more efficient than one single visit; you cannot remember many things at once”). Regarding accessibility, the difficulty with transportation to and from the museum, as well as the presence of stairs, were hindering factors for individuals with motor disabilities. Participants requested that information provided during the visit is more accessible, i.e., bigger letters in the texts accompanying the exhibits and access to printed material, and information about the exhibits (“I would like to learn all about the history of the exhibits, what inspired the artists, their thoughts”). As far as the use of technology is concerned, most participants had little or no experience with technologies when visiting a museum but were willing to try them out if the instructions were not complicated (“With the appropriate guidance I would like to listen to some audio-recordings of the exhibits’ description if they are synchronized with what I see”).

Results from the analysis of the physical status, cognitive status and mental wellbeing/quality of life measurements:

With regard to the assessment of the participants' physical status, the following results can be highlighted: The Tinetti test assesses an individual's perception of balance and stability during daily activities. The average score of study participants is almost 28, excellent, so they have a low risk of falls (when the score is between 25 and 28 it is considered that the examinee has a low risk of falling). The Berg Balance Scale measures balance, that is, a person's ability to achieve physical movement and perform activities of daily living. A score between 41 and 56 is considered to have a low risk of falling. The study participants fall into this classification as their scores range from 48 to 56. Functional strength of the lower extremity is assessed by the 30-second Chair Stand Test. Performance on this test correlates well with stair-climbing ability, walking speed, and fall risk. It is a safe and sensitive method in detecting age-related declines in strength and the effects of physical training in older adults. The 3 participants who had a score of 8, were in a risk zone. The Timed Up and Go Test (TUG) assesses mobility, balance, walking ability, and fall risk. The risk zone is 9 seconds and only one person was above this. We notice that people over 70 years completed the test in a longer time than those under 70, and this is something that is justified by the older age, but they are certainly nowhere close to the risk zone. Their aerobic capacity was assessed by the Two Minute Step test, one of several other alternatives. We observed that 2 of the 11 participants scored much better than the upper limit based on their age (they had very good aerobic capacity), 3 of them scored below the lower limit based on their age, and the remaining 6 had scores within the permissible limits set by the specific standards for the test. The Balance in One Leg Test assesses balance by considering the ability to maintain the body in fixed posture. When a person is able to stay more than 50" in this position they are considered to have excellent balance. Three of the participants have a time over 50" so they are in great condition. One participant is in the average range (32.88 secs), the other three have fair balance (between 10-24") and the last 4 have time below 10" which means their balance is very poor. The 10 Metre Walk Test is a performance measure used to assess walking speed in meters per second over a distance of 6 meters. It can be used to determine functional mobility, gait, and vestibular function. Seven participants up to 70 years old can walk at an average speed of 4,06 sec in normal pace and at an average speed of 3,06 sec in fast pace at this test. The meters per second (m/s) they cover are respectively 1.49 (normal pace) and 1.93 (fast pace). The four participants over the age of 70 can walk at an average speed of 5 sec

in normal pace and at an average speed of 4,13 sec in fast pace and the meters per second (m/s) they cover are respectively 1.2 (normal pace) and 1.47 (fast pace).

Regarding cognitive status, all the participants except one showed good cognitive status as per the (MMSE, MoCA). One participant with post-stroke aphasia was classified as having mild cognitive impairment. Overall, almost all participants scored very well on measures of short-term memory skills, verbal learning and memory, selective attention, cognitive flexibility, and processing speed (HVLIT, STROOP, TRAIL, Digit Span). Much lower scores were noted primarily for three of the eleven participants- the aphasic post-stroke patient and 2 other participants who had only 6 years of education.

Very high scores were also noted for almost all participants on measures of mental well-being and quality of life (GDS, STAI, VAS-Stress, VAS-Pain, WEMWBS, EQ-5D-5L, MFI). Notably, no perceived pain or anxiety was found for all but one participant. In addition, good scores were noted on measures related to the emotion and functioning aspects of mental wellbeing, as well as on dimensions of quality of life such as mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression, indicating a very good overall level of mental wellbeing and quality of life.

Results from the analysis of the questionnaires on the exhibit audio descriptions (original and modified/accessible):

Considering all the participants' responses to the questions related to the exhibit audio descriptions (original and modified/accessible), some important conclusions can be drawn. More specifically, almost all participants agreed that the standard guide was easy to understand and did not feel that it was long in terms of time, except for one participant, the last one (JRA3-011), who stated that it was a bit long. In regard to their responses to the questions relating to the words and sentences, some of them stated that both the words and sentences were simple, and they did not have any problems in understanding them. Some difficulties in comprehending the original audio guide were expressed by the first (JRA3-001), second (JRA3-002), seventh (JRA3-007), eighth (JRA3-008), and tenth (JRA3-010) participants, with the first two emphasizing that the words and sentences were possibly too many and they did not fully understand all of them.

Relatively similar results emerged for the modified/accessible audio guide. All but the seventh participant (JRA3-007) stated that they did not experience any difficulty with this audio guide, that it was relatively short in terms of time and that they understood it quite easily. They also reported that the sentences and words were not complex and that they were able to understand them easily. Small differences were found in the responses of the seventh participant (JRA3-007), who specifically stated that he did not easily understand the audio guide and considered it long. At the same time, he indicated that the sentences were somewhat long and complex, yet he understood them. His responses were similar for the words, which he also found slightly complex.

In general, the comments and feedback received by most participants (JRA3-002, JRA3-003, JRA3-004, JRA3-005, JRA3-006, JRA3-000, JRA3-011) stated that they preferred the modified/accessible audio guide more, while the rest expressed their preference for the original one, except for the seventh participant (JRA3-007) who stated that both audio guides seemed the same to him.

Results from the analysis of the data collected by the Smart watch and the Smart insoles: The data collected through the Smart watch included motion and orientation data in inactivity, total visit time and number of steps. The data collected from the Smart insoles, involved data such as number and length of steps, pace, contact time, foot swing time, speed, time of use, stability, balance, etc. All the above data are currently being analysed.

Results from the analysis of the data collected by the eye-tracking glasses:

Regarding the eye-tracking glasses, during the experiment, participants were asked to wear this system on their head while listening to the selected exhibits' audio description in order to collect data on eye movements, pupil dilation, gaze point and blinking to determine where participants focus their visual attention, what they are attending to and what they are ignoring. Although the selected exhibits were three, only the third exhibit, the West Pediment from the temple of Zeus at Olympia, was used for the analysis, due to the fact that its bigger/longer in width (8 meters) and height (3.15 meters) and it requires that the participants turn their head and not just the pupils of the eyes to focus on more specific and apparent details.

The two audio descriptions (original and modified/accessible) of the selected exhibit provided initially some general information about eye gaze and what it represents, and then some more specific information, e.g. where the participants were asked to focus. In that way, through the eye tracking system we were able to perceive at what time point they located it the locus of the information provided through the audio guide. In each of the two audio descriptions, we identified 4 specific points, where we expected the users to look at when listening to the audio description. We gave a margin from the time the participant completed the sentence with the point of interest of 4 to 5 seconds. Before starting with the analysis of results, we noted that one participant's video could not be included due to technical problems (JRA3-009) and only the results for the first (original) audio part are not included.

In both audio descriptions, we identified 4 points of interest which include the central point of the pediment which is the statue of Apollo and 3 more points to the right and the left of the statue. In the graphs that follow, the participants' response time for each point of interest we defined is presented. In both audio descriptions, 4 identical points of interest were defined, so a comparison is made between the two audio descriptions. In the following figure, the first point that set was the centre of the pediment where the Statue of Apollo is located. Based on the responses from both audio descriptions, all participants responded in less than 5 seconds except one participant who responded exactly within the maximum 5 seconds' limit. Also, for the simplified version one participant didn't respond at all. The average response time for all participants for the original audio was 2,513 seconds and the maximum 4,150 seconds and for the modified/accessible audio the average response time was 1,802 and maximum 5,110. From this comparison it appears that the modified/accessible audio description was more understandable since the average response time was smaller.

D7.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA3

Figure 19. Analysis of participants' time response for the centre of the pediment with the Pupil Core device between original and modified audio description

In the following images, some snapshots of the pediment are included. The green circle with the red centre indicates where the pupils of the participants focus.

Figure 20. Apollo

At the second point of interest, as you can see in the next graph (Figure 21), which refers to the right hand of Apollo, there was one participant that didn't respond in both audio descriptions (JRA0007). Also, the aphasic post-stroke participant (JRA0008), responded after 9,25 seconds for the original audio description, which is the maximum also response time. This participant, also never responded in the modified/accessible audio. In general, all the other responses from the participants were in average 3,221 seconds for the original audio and 1,847 seconds for the modified/accessible audio with maximum 4,150 seconds.

Figure 21. Right side of the statue of Apollo

D7.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA3

Figure 22. Analysis of participants' time response for the right hand of Apollo with the Pupil Core device between original and modified audio description

At the third point of interest, the description refers to the left of Apollo. For the original audio, 4 participants never responded and 2 of them exceeded the 5 seconds' limit. The average response time was 3,473 seconds and the maximum response time was 10,240 seconds. On the other hand, for the modified/accessible audio, we get better responses with average 1,138 seconds and maximum response 2,080 seconds and only one didn't responded.

Figure 23. Analysis of participants' time response for the left hand of Apollo with the Pupil Core device between original and modified audio description

At the fourth point of interest, which refers to the right of Apollo (Figure 24), only 4 participants exceeded the time limit, 1 participant never responded, and the average response time was 4,252 seconds and the maximum response time 10,190 seconds. In the modified/accessible audio description 4 participants exceeded the time limit and the average response time is 3,509 seconds and the maximum 7,230 seconds.

Figure 24. Left side of the Apollo, Theseus

Overall, the response times for the modified/accessible audio description were better than the original one, nearly 1 second and the maximum response time difference is nearly 4 seconds. There are two participants of particular interest since one of them (JRA008), only managed to respond immediately to one point of interest and in the rest either did not respond at all or exceeded the initial limit we had set. The other one (JRA007) responded to 3 of 8 points of interest in time, and on the others either did not respond at all or exceeded the initial limit we had set.

Figure 25. Analysis of participants' time response for the right of Apollo with the Pupil Core device between original and modified audio description

Results from the analysis of the feasibility and satisfaction questionnaire and overall visit experience:

The questions were the following:

1. Do you believe that your personal characteristics, for example, your age, gender, physical and mental abilities, made you a good participant for this study?

D7.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA3

2. Were you able to understand what you had to do during the study, e.g. the guidelines, tasks?
3. Were the tasks involved too difficult, e.g. using technology?
4. Did you complete the tasks in the time allowed?
5. In your opinion, was it easy for you to complete the tasks at the same time as your visit to the museum?
6. Did you feel safe during the study?
7. Did you feel that there were enough staff to accompany you during the study or to answer your questions?
8. Do you think that the measures that have been collected will be useful for people visiting the museum in the future?
9. How enjoyable do you consider your experience?
10. Would you recommend this experience to a friend?

The graphs below (Figure 25) show the answers to the feasibility and satisfaction questionnaire given to the participants of the study. On the vertical axis (y-axis) we depict the total number of participants who answered each question (11 participants in the study). The horizontal axis (x-axis) presents the possible answers to each question.

All the participants considered themselves a good fit for the study, in terms of age, gender, physical and mental abilities. More than half (54%) felt they were 'Extremely' right for it, and the rest (46%) felt they fit 'A lot'. Everyone understood what they needed to do and found the instructions easy to follow. A great majority (90%) didn't find the tasks hard at all, with only one participant (9%) saying the tasks were a bit hard. From the fourth question, we know that everyone felt able to finalize all the activities in the allotted time all participants noted that taking part in the experiment didn't disrupt their visit to the museum.

In looking at how the participants felt about safety during the study, nearly all of them, 10 out of 11, said 'Yes' to feeling safe (91%). Only one person (9%) felt unsafe. When it came to support from the staff, the same number, 91%, felt they had enough staff around to help them. Furthermore, every single participant believed that what they did in the study mattered. They all agreed that the actions taken would help future visitors. Finally, everyone enjoyed being part of the study since they found it pleasant and were willing to recommend it to others.

D7.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA3

Figure 26. Answers to the feasibility and satisfaction questionnaire

Conclusions

In conclusion, the results of the preliminary AUTH pilot study show that it is possible and feasible to use technological equipment for data collection in museum spaces, engaging healthy participants, but also patients, such as post-stroke patients, as in our case. Interestingly, almost all participants expressed satisfaction with their participation in this museum experience, felt safe during their visit and did not experience any significant difficulties, e.g. in using the technology.

On the other hand, despite the demonstrated feasibility, several obstacles were encountered by the researchers during the collection process. Challenges related to the recruitment of post-stroke participants, restrictions on access to the Museum of Casts and Antiquities, and limitations related

to the use of the museum's facilities, as well as challenges with collecting data from the eye-tracking glasses were reported by the research team.

Regarding the participants' understanding of the 2 audio descriptions of the selected exhibit, the general conclusion that can be drawn is that in the modified/accessible version, participants responded much faster compared to the original and with far fewer errors. In line with this conclusion are the participants' own responses regarding the extent to which they expressed that they understood the two audio guides, with some slight variations. Indeed, it appeared that the above conclusions were closely related to the educational level of the participants and their performance in the administered cognitive tests.

3. Harmonized Analysis across Living Labs

3.1. Living Lab harmonized services - Big Data Driven Hybrid Persona Development

Study description

Objective and Phases:

The aim of the JRA collaboration was to co-create and test a harmonized research protocol for developing big data-driven hybrid persona, which are hypothetical user archetypes created to represent a user community. There are three primary ways to define personas including (1) qualitative personas, (2) quantitative personas, and (3) qualitative personas with quantitative validation, also known as hybrid persona. This study focused on supporting hybrid persona creation with digital biomarker data.

Execution and Challenges

Progress and Barriers: “Expert opinions and advisory services” from the Living Lab were utilized to collect data on each Living Lab device. “Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping” services were employed to identify external expert panel members for the Delphi-panel. Additionally, “Small-scale real-life testing” services were indirectly utilized, as the JRA case studies provided real-life data on the usage of data collection devices in various settings. This data forms the foundation for evaluating the possibilities of creating hybrid personas.

The study was conducted as follows: First, the existing devices to collect qualitative and quantitative data via digital biomarkers were identified among all three JRAs living labs. Second, small-scale JRA case studies were conducted to evaluate the applicability of the selected tools to collect digital biomarkers in various rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday living environment settings. In parallel to case studies, as part of the Living Lab harmonization study, a modified online Delphi-study was conducted to define a taxonomy to categorize and organize the digital data collection and intervention tools employed by the case studies. Third, after completion of the case studies, the utilized devices were mapped according to taxonomy classification and examples on measurements and measurement intervals were collected to identify the possibilities for big data-driven hybrid persona creation. Finally, the challenges and benefits of using the devices to collect digital biomarker data were discussed with the case studies.

Outcomes and Analysis

Evaluation and KPIs: Consensus regarding the category definitions, whether definition was easy to understand and whether the item belongs to subcategory was measured by strongly disagree, disagree, agree, strongly agree, and no answer Likert-scale. The KPI for consensus was set to 70 % or higher agreement level for supermajority agreement and 80 % or higher for strong supermajority agreement.

Analysis: The resulting taxonomy includes 52 subcategories in three different layers. The first layer makes separation between 'data monitoring and collection' and 'intervention technologies'. The first one is then further divided into 'environmental' and 'human monitoring' and the latter one to 'Assistive technology,' 'Extended reality – XR (VR & AR)' and 'Serious games'. Only the 'human monitoring' includes the third layer, which consist of 'biometrics,' 'activity and behavioural monitoring,' 'cognitive ability and mental processes,' 'electrical bio-signals and physiological monitoring measures,' '(primary) vital signs,' and 'body size and composition.' Regarding to belongingness, 44 out of 52 items (84,6 %) achieved a strong supermajority level and 47 items received supermajority consensus level in the final 3rd Round. Results for easy to understand were somewhat similar, 43 items (82,7 %) gained strong supermajority and 49 items (94,2 %) ended up in supermajority level. As a result, the developed taxonomy is robust.

In total 65 devices were used in JRAs case studies (JRA1=22, JRA2=16, JRA3=26) while number of devices ranged from 1 to 12 between the cases. The utilized devices were mapped with taxonomy subcategories. As a result, 46 out of 52 (88 percent) subcategories were addressed in the case studies, thus indicating widespread opportunities to collect digital biomarker data for hybrid persona creation. The following measurement option were detected: 1) Continuous (e.g. 24h monitoring), Pre/Post, Short time duration (e.g. few minutes), Single event, Frequency, Event/Use/Activity duration (e.g. foot contact time, hours of sleep), Change triggered, Relative (e.g. % share of total), Response time, Cross reference to external data (e.g. weather). Sequenced, Amount (e.g. kg, number of steps) and Choice selection.

Conclusions

Challenges, Barriers & Lessons Learned, Recommendations:

There are widespread opportunities to utilize digital biomarker data for hybrid persona creation. The following opportunities, but not limited to, can be utilized when creating hybrid personas.

Real-time continuous monitoring enables real-time feedback and personalization as well as longitudinal data tracking. However, real-time data collection with high sampling frequency can quickly generate very large dataset, which might lead to high storage costs, information overload and processing speed issues. Therefore, caution should be exercised when collecting real-time data.

Pre/Post measurement helps comparing conditions and impact before and after specific events and interventions. **Short time duration** measurement can be used for capturing brief and critical moments. **Single event** measurement is suitable for recording specific incidents or occurrences and identifying isolated occurrences with potential consequence.

Frequency analysis helps identifying patterns and trends over time and creates understanding on the regularity of specific behaviours or events. **Event/Use/Activity duration** provides information on usage patterns and activity engagement as wells as gives information on the duration of specific activities or events. **Change triggered** measurement helps detecting and responding to significant changes in conditions and can be used for triggering alerts based on predefined thresholds. **Relative measurement** provides understanding on how successful conducted activity was or how results

compare for example to desired level. **Response time** evaluates how much time it takes to react to specific stimuli and can be used for evaluating cognitive processes, decision dynamics, and the efficiency of human performance.

Cross-references to external data enables seeking correlation to external factors which can enhance contextual understanding of the phenomenon. **Sequenced** data tracking be used to monitor the progression, evaluate timing and consistency of activities of specific actions. **Amount** measurement focuses on quantifying and measuring specific quantities and is useful for monitoring changes in amounts over time. **Choice selection** is recording user preferences or selections and gathers data on decision-making processes.

The list of the above measurement options is suggested to be used as a starting point when creating hybrid-user personas. The mapping of measurement options with the device taxonomy will interlink the outcome measures with measurement type.

3.2. JRA3 Comparative Results and Challenges

Comparative Results

To enable a comparative analysis across the studies undertaken in various living labs, a unified objective for the co-creation sessions was established, focusing on older adults experiencing both physical and cognitive health challenges. Methodologically, there was a concerted effort to standardize data collection methods, placing a strong emphasis on key areas such as quality of life, physical activity, mobility, social and emotional well-being, frailty, self-efficacy, and evaluations of usability.

In the ambit of Joint Research Activity 3 (JRA3), the investigations have been centred on the exploration and integration of cutting-edge technologies aimed at fostering Active and Healthy Ageing, alongside the development of methodologies for the novel use of smart environments, such as gyms tailored for older adults. This initiative is grounded in the aspiration to not only enhance the quality of life for the elderly but also to pioneer the implementation of smart environments that cater specifically to their needs.

The goal was to generate datasets and technologies of the highest quality, which could then be utilized to propel the field of Active and Healthy Ageing forward. The execution of these processes involved: i. The deployment of state-of-the-art technologies within living labs to monitor and support the daily activities of older adults; ii. The development and testing of methodologies that allow these environments to be adapted for new use cases, thereby expanding their applicability and impact.

General challenges

One of the main challenges encountered was the comparative analysis across different living lab environments. This analysis was critical for identifying the most effective technologies and methodologies for supporting Active and Healthy Ageing. To address this, we focused on: i. Harmonizing data collection measures across all living labs to ensure consistency and, as possible, comparability of the data collected; ii. Emphasizing the role of living labs in supporting the collection of measures relevant to the everyday living context of older adults. This included the harmonization of infrastructure and the identification of best practices for data collection.

Living Labs as Catalysts for Data Collection and Harmonization

Living labs played a pivotal role in the success of this endeavour by facilitating the harmonization of infrastructure necessary for data collection. Their unique position allowed for the creation of a supportive environment where measures for everyday living contexts could be collected efficiently and effectively. The living labs served not only as testbeds for the deployment of new technologies but also as hubs for the collection of valuable data that could inform future interventions and technologies aimed at supporting Active and Healthy Ageing.

3.3. Economic impact assessment

The VITALISE project based on the case studies analysed in previous sections assessed the impact of technological interventions on users' daily routines and well-being. The current section forms a socio-economic analysis, integrating cost-benefit considerations along with long-term implications.

By integrating the economic aspects associated with technology-supported living environments, the analysis concentrates on **assessing the sustainability and effectiveness of such interventions**. This approach provides decision-makers in healthcare, social services, and the aging population sector with current insights on the subject. Overall, this analysis aims to act as a benchmark for ongoing investments and collaborative endeavours in developing technology-driven solutions that can improve everyday living environments globally.

The recommendations derived from the research delineated within the current document can be divided into i) general, ii) recommendation for designing interventions for older adults and iii) recommendations for using technology in research.

I) **general recommendations**

- Personalization is key for effective interventions, especially in digital health technologies for older adults (Case Studies 1, 3, and 4).
- User engagement is crucial. Consider user needs and preferences when designing interventions (Case Studies 1 and 3).
- Conduct longitudinal studies to assess long-term effects (Case Study 3).
- Explore new technologies like AR and machine learning for more personalized interventions (Case Study 3).
- Address data privacy and security concerns to build trust (Case Study 4).
- Integrate with existing healthcare systems for better care coordination (Case Study 4).

II) **recommendations for designing interventions for older adults**

- Focus on attracting less active older adults who might benefit most (Case Study 1).
- Tailor the difficulty level of activities and programs (Case Study 1).
- Offer a wider variety of activities to sustain engagement over time (Case Study 1).
- Consider using familiar daily tasks for virtual reality simulations (Case Study 2).
- Develop educational materials and support to overcome technology adoption barriers (Case Study 4).
- Make physical fitness testing protocols easier to administer and analyse results (Case Study 4. LAUREA).
- Consider including cognitive assessments alongside physical fitness tests (Case Study 4 LAUREA).
- Offer testing services in locations frequented by less active older adults (Case Study 4 LAUREA).

III) **recommendations for using technology in research**

- Technological equipment can be feasible for data collection in museums with adjustments for space limitations and participant needs (Case Study 5).

D7.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA3

- Data collection methods should consider storage costs, processing speed, and participant burden (Living Lab harmonized services).
- Utilize various data collection methods (real-time, pre/post, etc.) depending on research goals (Living Lab harmonized services).

The above recommendations constitute the key takeaways from the research work performed within VITALISE addressed to **researchers and developers** that can assist them in sustaining the produced results and create in future more effective interventions and technologies for either the older adults and/or the broader population.

Focusing on the **cost aspects**, the initial investment encompasses expenses for **technology development, deployment, personnel training, and ongoing maintenance** across all case studies. These expenses are necessary for bringing new ideas to reality and guarantee their usefulness and efficiency in daily settings. On the **benefits** side, improved daily living activities can result in financial savings as they promote independence and lower the need for caregiver assistance. This not only improves the **quality of life** for users but also moderates societal burdens associated with the responsibilities of caregivers. Moreover, social services and healthcare organizations will be able to gather data in an improved manner that would make possible more informed decisions leading to more effective resource allocation and more precisely focused treatments. Consequently, optimized outcomes will be produced and potentially significant cost savings will occur in the long term.

Other aspects identified are the **enhanced user experiences** and **well-being** that would contribute to the **increase of productivity** and decrease of **healthcare costs**. Particularly, technology interventions have the potential to reduce the need for frequent medical interventions and support services by enabling individuals to better manage their health and daily routines. Moreover, healthcare and long-term care expenses are decreased when assistive technology is used to encourage independence among older persons. By fostering autonomy and self-reliance, these interventions not only improve the well-being of older adults but also alleviate pressure on healthcare systems and social services.

By proactively monitoring health indicators and providing timely interventions to older adults, remote monitoring technologies can prevent adverse health events and reduce the need for costly medical interventions. This would impact on the decreasing the number of hospitalizations and the usage of the healthcare facilities. Giving a bird's eye view on the long-term impact derived from the case studies the successful implementation of these interventions can lead to substantial **long-term cost savings** in every healthcare system implied to as well as respective social services. By addressing fundamental issues and enhancing results in daily life situations, these treatments establish the framework for a more resilient and effective healthcare system considering the population ageing particularly in high income countries. Information derived from World Health organization show that people worldwide are living longer and today most people can expect to live into their sixties and beyond. Every country in the world is experiencing growth in both the size and the proportion of older persons in the population. By 2030, 1 in 6 people in the world will be aged 60 years or over. At this time the share of the population aged 60 years and over will increase from 1 billion in 2020 to 1.4 billion. By 2050, the world's population of people aged 60 years and older will double (2.1 billion). The number of persons aged 80 years or older is expected to triple between 2020 and 2050 to reach 426 million. By 2050, two-thirds of the world's population over 60 years will live in low- and middle-income countries. The aforementioned data imply the imperative need of re-approaching the methods and techniques used in the health care domain and social services as the current ones would be soon unfordable to be preserved by the national health care systems in Europe and beyond. Besides, the cost reductions, these initiatives can increase the productivity encourage innovation in the healthcare industry and achieve economies of scale that multiply the positive economic impact.

VITALISE project contributes to economic growth by leveraging novel technology to address pressing societal needs while at the same promoting more quality of life among elder adults with their independence from caregivers. The empowerment of elder citizens' independence shall also reduce the strain on caregivers.

Concluding, this analysis underscores the significant potential of the VITALISE project's case studies to yield long-term benefits for individuals, communities, and healthcare systems. These initiatives set the basis for a more sustainable and inclusive future by supporting independence and well-being in daily living situations.

4. Recommendations for Everyday Living Environments

The VITALISE project's journey through co-creation phases and small-scale pilot activities has carved out a nuanced blueprint for enhancing everyday living environments to foster Active and Healthy Ageing (AHA). Throughout this process, each living lab contributed significant insights into the experiences and perceptions of various stakeholders involved in the utilization of technology for individuals with chronic illnesses. These insights have been pivotal in identifying potential enhancements in this domain.

Concrete findings from small-scale pilot activities have shed light on the impact and usability of technologies implemented in users' daily routines, revealing the profound potential of technology in improving the quality of life for older adults. The coordination and communication among different living labs and associated entities have played a critical role in harmonizing information gathering methodologies and operational approaches, aiming to enrich collective knowledge within the realms of innovation and research on a European scale.

Grounded in these insights, the project proposes a series of actionable recommendations for the Joint Research Action 3 on Everyday Living Environments. These recommendations emphasize the seamless integration of monitoring technologies into the daily lives of older adults, ensuring that these interventions are **non-intrusive** and uphold the utmost standards of **privacy and security**. The **adaptability and personalization** of technology to meet individual health statuses and preferences are highlighted as essential for enhancing autonomy and the quality of life, necessitating the development of **holistic monitoring solutions**. Such solutions should not only track physical health indicators but also encompass data relevant to social interactions and cognitive activities, offering a comprehensive view of an older adult's well-being.

Moreover, empowering older adults or any other user groups with user-friendly technologies to take an active role in their health management emerges as a pivotal aspect. This includes addressing and overcoming barriers to technology adoption by **simplifying user interfaces** and providing robust support systems. Technological interventions sustainability relies on continuous evaluation, feedback, and adaptation, underscored by a collaborative **co-creation process** involving end-users, caregivers, and healthcare professionals. The advocacy for policies facilitating integration of these innovative technologies into standard care practices further accentuates the importance of AHA.

The VITALISE Joint Research Actions, in this case specifically JRA3, strongly advocates for standardized data collection protocols and interoperability among monitoring devices to ensure robust and scalable interventions, embodying a commitment to enhancing everyday living environments through innovative technologies. This approach not only fosters an ecosystem conducive to Active and Healthy Ageing but also sets a precedent for future initiatives aimed at improving the lives of older adults through the integration of technology in daily living environments.

5. Conclusions

The journey through JRA3 has underscored the critical importance of integrating innovative technologies and methodologies within smart environments to support the ageing population, with a strong emphasis on the need for standardized data collection protocols and interoperability among monitoring devices. This advocacy is pivotal for ensuring robust and scalable interventions, aiming to enhance everyday living environments with innovative technologies. The comparative results have highlighted both the potential and the challenges of implementing such technologies in real-world settings. As we advance, refining these technologies and methodologies to be accessible, user-friendly, and capable of meeting the diverse needs of older adults becomes crucial. The insights gained from JRA3, bolstered by a commitment to standardization and interoperability, lay a solid foundation for future research and development in the quest to enhance Active and Healthy Ageing through smart environments, setting a precedent for future initiatives aimed at improving the lives of older adults through technology integration.

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